

High Resolution Lucky Imaging of Globular Cluster M3 with FastCam

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ABSTRACT

This report evaluates the potential of the ground based imaging method, Lucky Imaging¹ with the high speed detector FastCam, on the dense stellar field, Globular Cluster Messier Object M3. High-resolution I-band imaging of nine fields in the core of the cluster is presented and analysed. We report that this method is an effective way of obtaining astronomic and photometric results of crowded fields including bright stars, which compare well with similar studies using data from the Hubble Space Telescope (HST).

Data collected in both the Nordic Optical Telescope (NOT) and the William Herschel Telescope (WHT), both in Roque de los Muchachos, La Palma, is analysed yielding plate scales of 0.031" and 0.019" per pixel respectively. Near diffraction limited resolution is obtained with data from the NOT, 0.11", whereas WHT data achieves a resolution 3.7 times worse than the theoretical limit, 0.17". A study is made of the internal dynamics of the densest region of M3 where 24% of stars are observed to show movement with an average change of 1.99 milliarcseconds per year. A potential technique for the analysis of change of flux with time is discussed, focussing on a Blue Straggler. We present a new I magnitude Catalogue for stars detected by FastCam which is complete to magnitude 16.2. Up to this magnitude, star densities reach up to 0.54 stars per $arcsecond^2$ in the densest regions. The average photometric error across magnitudes 12 to 17 is found to be 0.117 mag, comparing favourably with a study made by Guhathakurta et. al. using HST data which quotes an error of 0.1 mag.

Keywords: Globular Clusters, M3, FastCam, Lucky Imaging, Speckle Imaging

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I. INTRODUCTION

Obtaining a high-definition image of a stellar field is one of the principal aims of the modern astronomer. This task is particularly difficult in dense stellar regions, such as in Globular Clusters where the fluxes of multiple close sources make reliable star detection problematic. This work focuses on the core of Globular Cluster Messier Object 3 (M3) and aims to provide high accuracy position and I magnitude information for over 300 stars through Lucky Imaging using FastCam. The data analysed here was taken during the commissioning phase of the project and as such is to be considered as a test of the method's capability with limited data. In comparison to later studies, the results here are obtained with approximately one tenth of the data typically collected for dense field imaging.

A. Aims

Obtaining precise information on stellar positions and magnitudes can shed light on many interesting characteristics of Globular Clusters. By comparing magnitudes from different filters, members of various stellar populations, such as the Blue Stragglers which are typical to M3, can be identified through Colour Magnitude Diagrams. A full star catalogue can give information as to the age of a Globular Cluster. By comparing photometric results collected over different dates, the period and variability of any variable candidates can be measured.

An in depth study of stellar motion within the centre of the cluster may provide clues as to the existence and nature of a central object. Objects in Globular Clusters orbit the centre in a largely random sense; if they were stationary the Cluster would collapse in on itself. It is suspected that black holes with mass $10^3 M_{\odot}$ may be the pivot point for Globular Clusters as proposed by McNamara et al. (2003). As found by Genzel et al. (2003) over a 16 year study, a Black Hole of $4 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ occupies the core of the Milky Way⁵. This was discovered by the accurate tracking of 28 stars in the surrounding area. If a similarly persuasive study can be made of the densest regions of Globular Clusters it is hoped that a similar conclusion can be reached as to the characteristics of the central body. The Hubble Space Telescope has been used to carry out a similar investigation focused on Globular Cluster Omega Centauri as previous research had strongly suggested the presence of a large black hole. Data from 2002 and 2006 was compared to analyse the internal dynamics and it was concluded that the existence of a central black hole was less likely than believed. If indeed a black hole is the central body, a mass as large as that proposed is highly improbable.

This project investigates the potential of Lucky Imaging using FastCam, a ground-based technique which theoretically provides diffraction limited images. Diffraction limited resolution is the maximum achievable definition and This method is described in depth in the following sections. I-band data gathered in May, 2008 is analysed, generating a new star catalogue for the core of M3. Since only I-band data is available, the results will be compared to those of pre-existing catalogues to ascertain the accuracy of the technique. It is hoped to achieve results comparable to these catalogues within 0.2 magnitudes. A study of stellar movement is also carried out to detect any dominant direction of internal motion. It is expected that a diffraction limited angular resolution be achievable with this technique, in both the 2.5m Northern Optical Telescope and the 4.2m William Herschel Telescope. Previous studies using this same technique have had positive results. We aim to achieve results to indicate that Lucky Imaging with FastCam is a viable, low-budget alternative to high spatial resolution imaging from space. In particular, this study will show the potential of the method with comparatively little data to later studies.

B. The Limits of Angular Resolution

The resolving power of a telescope is proportional to the size of the aperture, hence telescopes have been increasing in size in an effort to resolve the close members of dense fields. Angular resolution is defined by the following equation:

$$\theta \propto \frac{\lambda}{D} \quad (1)$$

where θ is the angular resolution, λ is the wavelength of the electromagnetic energy being observed and D is the diameter of the telescopic aperture. θ is considered to be a suitable approximation for $\sin \theta$ since all angles considered are small.

Whilst the size of the telescope plays its part in determining the resolution of an image, there are various other contributing factors. These include air-inhomogeneity, alignment errors and forced telescope surface deformations⁷. These secondary factors tend to dominate, limiting resolution. Air-inhomogeneity in particular causes severe difficulty when imaging dense stellar fields. A perfect image of a star can only be made if the entire wave-front of the electromagnetic flux radiated by the star preserves its form. If a star is treated as a point source, the wave-front can be said to be emitted as a sphere. Due to the vast distances between us and neighbouring stars, the perceived wave-front on earth can be approximated as a plane. Prior to arriving at the detector, every wave-front passes through the atmosphere. Our atmosphere is a highly inhomogeneous medium due to the combination of thermal currents and wind. Thermal columns of air rise through the atmosphere whilst winds simultaneously cause transversal variations in density. As a result of these oscillations in air density, sections of the wave-front travel along optical paths of different lengths. Figure 1 provides a graphical representation of atmospheric dispersion.

FIG. 1: Graphical representation of atmospheric dispersion of stellar flux⁷. r is the mean diameter of a homogeneous air pocket and D is the diameter of the telescope.

Whilst these wave-front distortions are largely random, a mean variation can be considered in terms of atmospheric-coherence length. This term is the average length of an atmospheric region in which a single transformation is made on the incoming radiation. For example, in one stretch of atmosphere all photons may be refracted through a certain angle whilst in a neighbouring region they may be refracted through an entirely different angle. This length is termed the Fried Parameter, shown as r in Figure 1. A larger Fried parameter means better seeing as more coherent light is incident on the telescopes. Seeing due to atmospheric turbulence can be described mathematically as

$$d \propto \frac{\lambda}{r} \quad (2)$$

where λ is the wavelength and r is the Fried Parameter. Seeing refers to the average Full Width Half Max of a star in a long exposure image and reflects the refractive index of the atmosphere. A lower seeing indicates better imaging conditions, i.e. low turbulent mixing in the atmosphere. A night with high seeing will show a greatly dispersed speckle image, speckle images are discussed below in detail. In a diffraction limited telescope, neglecting atmospheric dispersion, seeing can be stated as seen in Equation 1.

By direct comparison of Equations 1 and 2 it can be seen that when the diameter of a telescope exceeds the Fried Parameter it ceases to be limited by angular resolution but by atmospheric dispersion. As seen in the following equations, seeing improves with increasing wavelength once the diameter of the telescope has exceeded the Fried Parameter, r . Equation 3 shows the relationship between the Fried Parameter and the wavelength of light. Equation 4 demonstrates the correlation of seeing to the Fried parameter and in turn, the

wavelength.

$$r \propto \lambda^{\frac{6}{5}} \quad (3)$$

$$d \propto \frac{\lambda}{r} \propto \lambda^{-\frac{1}{5}} \quad (4)$$

The flux from an individual star or source will arrive scattered at the detector in a range of positions, depending upon the amount of atmospheric dispersion to which sections of the wave-front are subjected, forming a Speckle Image as seen in Figure 2. These images are only visible when using an exposure of $\frac{1}{4}$ of a second or less. This is the average time period in which a pocket of atmosphere remains in a steady state, hence by looking at time periods less than this, there is a high probability of the light remaining approximately constant across the integration time. At time periods longer than this, a seeing limited image is observed. The most defined speckles, i.e. the most circular individual points within the speckle image, have a diffraction-limited Point Spread Function (PSF) defined by the telescope's diameter. When allowed a long exposure time, the individual speckle images accumulate and smear out, becoming a seeing-limited image. This seeing-limited star image has a spatial resolution which is independent of the size of the telescope but rather is determined by the Fried Parameter. A 2.5m telescope is limited by atmospheric dispersion to around a 0.5 arcsecond resolution, ten times worse than the theoretical limit based on telescopic dimensions⁶.

FIG. 2: Speckle images due to atmospheric dispersion, wave-front distortion⁷ at very small time intervals, millisecond separation.

C. Countering Atmospheric Dispersion

Several methods to reduce the effect of atmospheric dispersion have been attempted with varying degrees of success. The most successful high resolution imaging technique is to make astronomical measurements beyond the reaches of the atmosphere; to use the Hubble Space Telescope (HST), or the future James Webb Space Telescope (JWST). Whilst the quality of such images cannot be faulted, the associated costs limit usage and lengthy studies are impractical. Finding a cheap, ground based alternative is of great scientific importance for the continued investigation of dense stellar fields.

An important consideration, when planning the location of a ground based observatory, is the level of atmospheric dispersion at the site. Mountain positions, above temperature inversion layers and with stable, laminar prevailing winds create the perfect environment for maximum seeing. The Nordic Optical Telescope and the William Hershel Telescope (WHT), both located in Roque de los Muchachos in La Palma, provide ideal seeing conditions. The laminar prevailing wind is provided by the stable temperature gradient above the hundreds of kilometres of Atlantic Ocean which surround the Canary Islands. Figure 3 shows the ideal location for an observatory.

FIG. 3: Comparison of seeing. Ideal location on mountain peak for limited atmospheric dispersion¹¹

One correction technique uses Fourier Transforms to resolve close companions. After applying the transforms, stellar profiles may resemble interference patterns similar to those seen from double slits. These fringes are analysed and individual close companion stars can be identified. This has been of little practical use other than in resolving binary stars.

Adaptive Optics has been of great practical success for a large number of projects⁸. Distortions in the wave-front are calculated at the detector and are compensated for by a spatial phase modulator. One possible modulator is a flexible mirror which reconfigures according to the distortion measured at the detector in an effort to produce a uniform wave-front. Many larger telescopes i.e. those with a diameter larger than the Fried Parameter, have been developed with integrated adaptive optics systems to minimise the effects of atmospheric dispersion in images with high definition, high dynamic range and high spatial resolution². The Gran Telescopio de Canarias (GTC), in La Palma, is one such telescope. With a diameter of 10.4 meters it is currently the largest in the world and implements an Adaptive Optics System. As the wave-front enters the telescope it first passes through a wave-front sensor which sends a signal to an array of 42 mirrors below. This initial data defines a flexibility for the mirrors and allows for the wave-front to be reconstructed once inside the detector. The WHT also features integrated adaptive optics and is the source of some of the data analysed here.

FIG. 4: Laser Guide Star at the Paranal in Chile, taken by Yuri Beletsky.

A bright, well calibrated reference star is needed as a guide for the system hence this method is limited to very specific situations. As an alternative to a reference star, a laser can effectively generate a point source. The laser, a 589.2nm sodium laser being the most widely used, is projected from the telescope as shown in Figure 4. At approximately 90km a layer of sodium ions in the mesosphere absorbs the laser and re-emits photons randomly creating an artificial star. The laser is commonly pulsed to create this effect. This light propagates back through the atmosphere and is subject to the same refractive effects as its natural companions. As the exact properties of this "star" are well known, the location and flux, the effect of atmospheric turbulence can be subtracted across the entire field.

These adaptive methods are primarily designed to operate in the near infrared bands; J, H and K. In the optical range additional data is required and results are generally less reliable. Infrared and near-infrared imaging is easier as the time scales at which the photons are affected by the atmosphere are larger, allowing adjustments in the telescope's mirrors to be valid for marginally longer periods. One main drawback of Adaptive Optics is that the reliable field of view is often too small to be of practical scientific use. However, this method routinely generates diffraction limited images useful for a large variety of scientific applications.

One disadvantage of Adaptive Optics is that it demonstrates limited capability at visual wavelengths. An interesting alternative which has been found to generate accurate results in the visual spectrum is Lucky Imaging.

D. Lucky Imaging

In the 1960s Bob Hufnagel began pioneering research into atmospheric turbulence. This work included a study of what later became known as Lucky Imaging probabilities. Shortly afterwards David Fried, whose name is given to the seeing parameter described in Section IC, published a paper quantifying turbulence and extending the research which eventually lead to the method used in this work. The advent of new detectors with very low readout noise was crucial for the expansion of the technique to its current capability. By taking very short exposure images, exploiting the sensitivity of these detectors, the turbulence of the atmosphere can effectively be frozen yielding sharp speckle images⁹. A fraction, up to 10%, of these images capture moments of extremely good seeing in which the stellar field being observed is seen with excellent resolution. Isolating and combining these images is the basic method followed to produce images with near diffraction limited angular resolution. This process can include millions of speckle images each with an exposure length of a few tens of milliseconds from which the best are selected via a computer based algorithm. In the past decade, preliminary runs were made with Lucky Imaging technology¹, with very successful outcomes.

FIG. 5: FastCam analysis software

The thousands of 2D images are grouped in 3D files called cubes, in which all images are ordered chronologically. A pixel region within the individual images in each cube is assigned as the valid area inside which the brightest pixel can fall for the image to be selected. The images which have the brightest speckles, restricted to those which fall inside the specified region, are combined using a *shift-and-add* method. The images in which a large amount of light is concentrated in one spatial point coincide with incidents of lower atmospheric dispersion. The final stellar profile consists of a diffraction-limited core, the addition of all the selected bright speckles, surrounded by a seeing-disk, which is a result of the fainter speckles which surround the centre. Mathematically, this "Point Spread Function (PSF)" most closely resembles combined Lorentzian and Moffat function. Figure 6 demonstrates the clear quality of speckle images processed with Lucky Imaging as opposed to long exposure seeing-images.

FIG. 6: Comparison of single speckle image, long exposure seeing-image and Lucky Imaging processed image (viewed left to right).¹⁵ A resolved binary star can be clearly seen in the final image.

A compromise on telescope size must be made when making observations for Lucky Imaging. A telescope's diameter must exceed the Fried Parameter at the desired wavelength for the method to be of benefit but, conversely, the larger the diameter, the lower the probability of capturing a frame of very low atmospheric dispersion⁶. 2.5m telescopes have been found to produce successful Lucky Imaging results, such as the Nordic Optical Telescope in La Palma, Spain. Here, Lucky Imaging using the William Herschel Telescope is also discussed, with the hope of verifying the method's potential using a 4m diameter telescope. The WHT features integrated adaptive optics and, by combining this with Lucky Imaging, even higher resolution should be achievable. Researchers from the LuckyCam (similar to FastCam,) team at Cambridge University have had unparalleled success when using Lucky Imaging combined with Adaptive Optics in the 5.1m Palomar Telescope, California. Since the method provides diffraction limited resolution, an angular resolution of 35 milliarcseconds was achieved in the optical, twice that of the 2.5m Hubble Space Telescope. This is currently the highest ever angular resolution achieved, emphasising the capability and potential of Lucky Imaging¹².

Although Lucky Imaging provides an impressive alternative to high spatial resolution imaging from space, it does have its drawbacks. In order for a precise photometric calibration to be made, the target field must contain bright stars to be matched with well defined stars from other catalogues. At least one bright star, with magnitude greater than ≈ 14 , must be present within each cube of data to act as the reference star from which to define and select the best seeing images. Currently, the attainable field of view is limited, and for many investigations various pointings must be made to form a mosaic of astronomic images. The clear advantage of Lucky Imaging over imaging from space is that results are not affected by saturation; combining multiple short exposure images eliminates the possibility of saturation, facilitating the detection of close star companions.

E. FastCam

FastCam has been developed by the Universidad Politecnica de Cartagena and the Instituto de Astrofisica de Canarias, both in Spain, and is generally to be found as a common-user instrument in the 1.5m Carlos Sanchez Telescope in the Teide Observatory, Tenerife, Spain. Due to its compact size and versatility, it is possible to use FastCam in a large range of telescopes such as the 2.5m Nordic Optical Telescope, NOT, or the 4.2m William Herschel Telescope, WHT. FastCam data from both of these sources is processed and analysed in this report.

FastCam's detector is a fast readout Electron Multiplying Charge Coupled Device, (EM)CCD, developed by Andor Technology designed for low intensity imaging². This camera generates images of 512 x 512 pixels and is capable of capturing data on time scales from hundreds to a few tens of milliseconds. Cooling to a temperature below -80°C is provided with a Pettier System. Through Electron Multiplication, the true stellar signals are outputted with very low noise, as low as 1 - rms in each pixel compared to useful signal count. The quantum efficiency of FastCam's detector varies over the electromagnetic spectrum and peaks at 550nm, though this depends on the sensor option selected for the instrument. See Figure 7 for a graphical representation of quantum efficiency across the wavelength range. The detector is coupled with a simple optics device which accommodates different plate scales in a range of telescopes. Data was collected using Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) processing and acquisition hardware.

FIG. 7: Quantum Efficiency (QE) of FastCam’s detector. Labels refer to different sensor options, BV is QE of the back illuminated sensor for Visible, UVB is optimised for Ultra-Violet radiation and BB is optimised in the blue with an anti-reflective coating.

When used operationally, FastCam is mounted in a compact frame which incorporates two filter wheels. This allows different energy ranges to be observed by changing the filter and facilitates the collection of colour magnitude data. Due to the simplicity of the design, FastCam is compatible with a large number of telescopes of varying diameters. FastCam has so far been used in telescopes ranging from 1.5 to 4.2m in diameter. Figure 8 shows FastCam in its standard configuration, with the detector on the right hand side². The data presented here was collected using an I-band filter. FastCam collects anywhere up to millions of images with millisecond exposure times which are then processed using a custom made software, see Figure 5, which implements the Lucky Imaging technique. Over the past few years, work with FastCam has included high contrast imaging of sub-stellar companions, Labadie et al. (2010)², and high precision astrometry of a brown dwarf binary, Femenia et al. (2010)³.

FIG. 8: FastCam camera on its support. The Speckle detector can be seen on the right hand side.²

F. Lucky Imaging PSF

Lucky Imaging requires the specification of the number of frames in each cube of images to be selected for the final image. By varying the percentage maintained, the size and shape of the central core and seeing disk are found to alter. As seen in Figure 9, the blue line represents a seeing image and the black line represents the PSF when 10 out of 1000 frames are kept.

The FastCam images analysed here were made using a 7% threshold. The light blue line in Figure 10 shows the PSF profile taken from Field 2, see Figure 17 for information. The PSF is clearly not a typical, gaussian curve, but is more accurately described as a superposed or summed Moffat and Gaussian. The Moffat can be described mathematically as

$$Moffat = \frac{b-1}{\pi a^2} \times \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y}{a}\right)^2\right)^{-b} \quad (5)$$

where a and b are constants which can be changed to alter the Moffat’s height and width and x and y are the pixel coordinates. The Gaussian can be described as

$$Gaussian = h \times e^{-\left(\frac{x^2}{2s^2} + \frac{y^2}{2s^2}\right)} \quad (6)$$

where h and s are constant parameters and x and y are once again pixel coordinates. As seen in Figure 10, the sum of a Gaussian and Moffat (the red crosses, formed by summing the blue Moffat and the green Gaussian,) provides a reasonable model for the PSF, despite the stellar profile being affected by noise producing slight asymmetry. The superposition, viewed by combining the pink Gaussian with the blue Moffat also models the PSF with a fair degree of accuracy though in this case the sum appears to yield a truer fit.

FIG. 9: PSF as a function of percentage frames kept in a cube for the NOT. From Femenia et al 2010.

FIG. 10: The stellar profile of FastCam images. True PSF taken from one image shown in light blue, Moffat shown in dark blue and large Gaussian shown in purple. Neither the Moffat nor the large Gaussian provide an adequate model for the PSF. Red crosses show the sum of the small Gaussian, in green, and the Moffat and clearly provides a reasonable fit to the true PSF. An average pixel difference between the model and the true PSF of 0.00032 is achieved with the summed curves as opposed to 0.01192 with the superposed curves.

G. Wavelet Filtering

The FastCam Stellar Profile consists of a diffraction limited core surrounded by a wide, pale halo. The PSF can be modelled as summed, or superimposed Gaussian and Moffat functions as shown in Figure 10. This halo, the faint seeing disk, which extends well beyond the core, can interfere with the flux from neighbouring stars, obscuring close companions and preventing accurate measurements. The halo is similarly present in images created using Adaptive Optics due to imperfect corrections of the wave-fronts². A technique in common usage within Astrophysics is Wavelet Convolution² which adds definition to close stellar objects. By convolving FastCam images with a 3D Mexican Hat (the Laplacian of the Gaussian,), the central peak of each star can

be emphasised whilst the faint surrounding disk effectively sinks into the background of the field²³. All saddle points are diminished whilst maxima are accentuated. Figure 11 shows a Mexican Hat with total width of 30 pixels and a central Gaussian of width 3.

This filter can be represented mathematically as,

$$MH(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^4} \left(2 - \frac{x^2 + y^2}{\sigma^2} \right) \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (7)$$

where x and y are the pixel coordinates of the Wavelet and σ defines the width of the central peak. Effectively, the Mexican Hat is the normalised, negative, second derivative of the Gaussian and was found to be particularly effective in exposing objects in dense stellar fields²³. The maximum, at coordinates x and y equal to 0 has a magnitude of

$$\text{maximum magnitude} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}\sigma\pi^{\frac{1}{4}}} e \quad (8)$$

where e is the exponential to the power of 1. The minima, surrounding the central peak at a radial distance of $\pm\sigma\sqrt{3}$, have magnitude

$$\text{minimum magnitude} = \frac{-4}{\sqrt{3}\sigma\pi^{\frac{1}{4}}} e^{-\frac{3}{2}} \quad (9)$$

By altering σ , the amount by which the peaks and troughs are emphasised can be controlled.

FIG. 11: Mexican Hat Filter used to convolve FastCam images

This Wavelet is particularly useful in our case due to its origins in Gaussian signal: as the Laplacian of the Gaussian it is well adapted to amplify the Gaussian, diffraction limited core of our images²⁴. By changing the width and the amplitude of the Mexican Hat it is possible to find an optimum filter for a particular image. These optimal parameters vary according to the definition of the original image and, in our case, is related to the number of cubes of data reduced. This Wavelet is highly robust, so much so that it is almost equally effective in a noisy field as in one with a negligible background signal.

The FastCam PSF is changed noticeably by the Mexican Hat Wavelet. Considering the ideal, circular PSF achieved in some fields, the effect is seen as a clear sharpening of the diffraction limited core. Figure 12 shows the observed PSF before and after Wavelet filtering. Figure 13 displays a vertical cut through the PSF, demonstrating the clear change in profile shape. This effect depends upon the parameters chosen for the Wavelet used.

FIG. 12: Wavelet Filtered PSF (left,) and Original PSF (right.)

FIG. 13: PSF profile, before and after Wavelet application. The PSF can be seen to take on the form of the Mexican Hat with a small dip surrounding the core.

H. Globular Cluster M3

Globular clusters are some of the oldest objects in our universe, their ages are estimated to be in the region of 12 billion years and stellar populations can be as large as 10^6 stars pc^{-3} . Developing from what were once just large volumes of gas and dust, Globular Clusters are now dense stellar fields primarily composed of Population II stars. These stars tend to be fairly small and are located towards the red end of the spectrum with low metallicity, giving an indication of their age. Due to the relatively high probability of collisions and stellar encounters, many examples of uncommon objects such as binaries and pulsars have been located in clusters. There has been some indication that Globular Clusters may be home to black holes though this claim has yet to be rigorously proved. It is predicted that by studying stellar movement in the central regions, a large gravitational source could be revealed.

M3, Messier Object 3, is one of such Globular Clusters and is located at RA (J200) = 13:42:11, Dec (J200) = +28:22:32, 33,900 light years away in the constellation Canes Venatici. It was first logged by Charles Messier on May 3rd 1764 as the 76th deep sky object¹⁶. Twenty years later, William Herschel resolved M3 into separate stars and it was recorded as a Globular Cluster. In general, M3 is a large, reasonably low density cluster which spans 760 light years in diameter, 16.1 arcminutes, but has a highly dense core measuring only 11 light years. It is this core that has proved a challenge to measure with high resolution, definition and dynamic range using traditional techniques and which has been investigated here with FastCam. M3 is a good field for Lucky Imaging analysis due to its high number of bright stars; these stars act as reference stars in the frame selection process and aid in matching the field with pre-existing images for calibration. Shawl and White (1986) determined the centre of M3 to be located at 13:42:11.18 +28:22:31.5 with less than 0.5" uncertainty. Figure 14 shows an image of M3 made by Robert J. Vanderbei.

FIG. 14: M3, taken by Robert J. Vanderbei on March 12th, 2007.

M3 contains stars of a wide range of magnitudes, the brightest are of around magnitude 12 and the average magnitude of the twenty five brightest stars has been calculated to be 14.23. Generally in Globular Clusters, the heavier stars sink to the centre leaving the lighter on the outskirts. There has been some dispute as to the spectral type of M3, with F2 and F7 both being postulated¹⁶. Metallicity has been calculated to be approximately -1.50 on the FeII metallicity scale¹⁹. The cluster has been estimated to contain as many as half a million stars though the exact number is unknown. On a clear night, M3 can be seen by the naked eye though even the largest telescopes experience problems when trying to resolve the very core via classic methods.

Several Stellar Catalogues have been made of M3, one of the most thorough being that of Guhathakurta et. al. 1992⁴. Guhathakurta used the Hubble Space Telescope's Wide Field/Planetary Camera-I instrument to make accurate measurements of I, V and U magnitudes in the centre of M3. A photometric accuracy of 0.1 mag was reported and 28 Blue Straggler stars, all with periods above 8 hours, were located within the central 0.29 arcmin. This catalogue is used in this report for astrometric and photometric comparison with FastCam data. The cluster has been observed for studies focussing on a large range of stellar populations, some of which are discussed below.

1. Blue Stragglers

In the 1950's, Allan Sandage analysed the Hertzsprung-Russel diagram of Globular Cluster M3 for his dissertation and discovered a high number of anomalous stars which he named Blue Straggler Stars (BSS). BSS are stars which are bluer, hence appearing younger by emitting flux at higher energies, than stars in the main sequence and tend to be found in dense fields. It is believed that they acquire their unexpected luminosity through close encounters with other stars. The likelihood of such incidents is highest in dense regions such as the core of M3. There are various theories as to how Blue Stragglers are born. One of the theories with greatest support is that they are, or were, binary stars in the process of merging. The new star, the combination of both binary members, would have a greater mass than those of the main sequence, and hence appear younger. It is hoped to test this theory by measuring the magnitude variations of Blue Stragglers, theoretically they may reflect the fact that they are made of two or more individual stars. Fast rotation would support this collision theory and has been observed in some test cases.

2. Variable Stars

M3 is known for its high number of Variable Stars. Over 270 variables have so far been found in the core, the vast majority of which have well documented periods. This includes 170 RR Lyrae candidates. RR Lyraes are horizontal branch stars, generally of spectral class A and of approximately half a solar mass. In a Colour Magnitude Diagram (CMD) they are situated on the intersection of the instability strip and the horizontal branch. There is a well defined relationship between period and luminosity such that RR Lyraes are often used as standard candles to calculate distances between nearby objects. RR Lyrae variables typically have a pulsation period of less than one day, ranging down to a few hours, and tend to have luminosity around 45 times that of the sun¹⁸. Their magnitude oscillations range between 0.3 and 2 magnitudes. M3 is classified as a type I Oosterhoff cluster, reflecting the average RR variable period of 0.55 days¹⁹. Due to their frequent detection in Globular Clusters, RR Lyraes have been called Cluster Cepheids or Short-Period Cepheids. Cepheids are a subtly different group of variable stars. As a general rule, Cepheids are larger and have greater periods and luminosities than RR Lyraes. They are also found further off the main sequence in CMDs.

3. X-Ray Sources

Globular Clusters are also breeding grounds for X-Ray Sources. Over 1500 X-Ray Sources have been found in little over 80 Galactic Clusters. It has been discovered that High Luminosity X-Ray sources are in fact neutron stars accreting matter from a smaller companion obtained via primordial binary collisions or tidal capture¹⁴. Low Luminosity X-Ray Sources (LLXRS), on the other hand, are little understood. M3, a relatively open cluster, was the target for an in depth study of a LLXRS by Hertz, Grinday and Bailyn¹⁴. The source, 1E1339.8+2837 is located on the edge of the core, approximately 25" from the centre. Whilst the study was successful in aiding understanding of LLXRS, concluding that the source is probably a cataclysmic variable (a white dwarf accreting matter from a close companion resulting in sharp increases in flux,), the spatial resolution on the source location is too low to facilitate a search for an optical counterpart within this study.

4. Pulsars

Currently, 4 Pulsars have been found within M3, two of which appear to be binaries. In general, approximately 130 pulsars have been found across all Globular Clusters in a 1.4GHz Arecibo Survey²⁰. Both Millisecond Pulsars and longer period Pulsars are routinely found in such environments, these Pulsars have been used in a study to try and prove the existence of black holes in Clusters but was inconclusive.

II. OBSERVATIONS AND DATA REDUCTION

A. Observations

1. Observations in the WHT

The data analysed in this report was collected over various nights in May of 2008. On the 22nd of May, 10 cubes of 1000 images were taken of M3 from the 4.2m William Herschel Telescope at Roque de los Muchachos, La Palma. A further field was also observed in the same region but, due to extremely poor image quality, has not been analysed here. Seeing conditions were reported to be poor, as recorded in the observing log, with the telescope was centred on 13:42:09.3,+28:22:46.9, and focus was normal. Figure 15 shows the altitude of M3 during the night of the 22nd of May. The field maintained good altitude during a long observing period and was only marginally affected by lunar contamination.

FIG. 15: M3 Observability, 22nd of May from Roque de los Muchachos. Dashed line represents moon whilst complete line represents path of M3.

2. Observations in the NOT

Moving to the 2.5 Nordic Optical Telescope, also at Roque de los Muchachos, data was collected from a further eight fields within M3 on the 28th and 29th of May 2008. 32 cubes of 1000 images were collected centred on what is supposed to be the very core of the cluster, 13:42:11.3 +28:22:35.6, on the 28th. Three more fields were observed in this same region. Details of the number of cubes taken of each field can be found in Table 17. On the 29th, four further fields were observed. See Figure 17 for a visual representation of all FastCam pointings. Object observability was very good, again with low lunar contamination. Focus was reported as normal on both nights though there was a 10m/s wind recorded on the 28th.

All images from both NOT and WHT had an exposure time of 30ms and were taken using an I-band filter. Figure 16 shows the transmission response curve of the I-band filter used in FastCam thereby defining a range of wavelengths detected, approximately 750 - 1000nm.

FIG. 16: Flux Transmission with I-band Filter. Filter used in FastCam for all data analysed here.

B. Data Reduction in the NOT and WHT

Our cubes of data were reduced via Lucky Imaging, using the software depicted in Figure 5. The following process was repeated for all fields, from both the WHT and the NOT, which are depicted in Figure 17. For a single field, each cube was loaded individually and visually scanned to locate one star which was uniformly brightest across the vast majority of all 1000 images. This star was taken to be the reference star for the particular cube. A circular region, 55 pixels in diameter, was placed around this star, defining the valid area in which the brightest pixel of an individual image could fall for it to be considered a good-seeing image. The software was run to select the brightest 7% of all images. 70 individual images were selected from each cube, these images were considered those with best seeing which is characterised by a strong diffraction limited speckle.

Our selected images were combined by locating the brightest pixel in each and implementing a shift-and-add method. In this way a defined image was created for each cube. Within a single field, these images from all cubes were combined using shift-and-add to generate the final image. Once again a limiting region of 55 pixels was defined, in which the brightest pixel had to fall for the image to be used, to avoid large shifts. A very large shift would cause inconsistency in the background and magnitude of the stars, as there would be areas composed of fewer individual frames hence altering the time exposure and quality. As a final measure to avoid this, a border of 55 pixels was removed from each image thereby eliminating the potential problems due to large shifts. In this way we obtained a final image of 402 x 402 pixels for each stellar field. The final integration time for each image was dependent on the number of cubes, with each cube providing 2.1 seconds of exposure. Several cubes had to be discounted due to extreme background noise, severe profile elongation, large shift or poor image quality; the final number of cubes used for each field is detailed below along with integration time in Table 17.

FIG. 17: Fields observed by FastCam superimposed on image of M3 taken by the HST. All fields observed by FastCam. Field 8 is from the William Herschel Telescope whilst the remaining are from the Nordic Optical Telescope.

Field	Date	Telescope	Total Cubes	Cubes Used	Int. Time (s)
1	28/05/08	NOT	31	31	65.1
2	28/05/08	NOT	30	28	58.8
3	28/05/08	NOT	32	7	14.7
4	28/05/08	NOT	10	10	21.0
5	29/05/08	NOT	29	24	50.4
6	29/05/08	NOT	14	6	12.6
7	29/05/08	NOT	21	14	29.4
8	22/05/08	WHT	10	8	16.8
9	29/05/08	NOT	10	7	14.7

TABLE I: Field details including Integration time. Fields labelled as seen in Figure 17

To improve object definition, the Mexican Hat Filter, as described in detail in Section IG, was applied to the final images. Here, the Wavelet was implemented using two distinct methods. Multiple methods were used as a slight difference in Wavelet form can have an great impact on the filtered image and an optimal filter should be found for each image, the parameters of which may vary. The first method makes use of a Mexican Hat of the same dimensions as the image; in our case 402 x 402 pixels. A Fourier Transform is applied to both the image and the filter which are then multiplied together and deconvolved. In these "Full Width" filters only the width of the peak can be varied. The second method uses IDL's CONVOL routine²⁶. This uses the Mexican Hat as a kernel which it centres over each data point before evaluating the transformation. Here both the width of the Mexican

Hat and the width of its peak can be altered, varying the definition of the convoluted image. Figure 18 is of Field 3 after complete data reduction and Figure 19 shows examples of different Wavelets applied to said field.

FIG. 18: Field 3, final image after data reduction before Wavelet filtering. The centre is located at 13:42:10.75 +28:22:40.5.

Whilst Figure 18 does show reasonable resolution, it can be improved upon by filtering. Anomalous elongation of the stellar profile is also observed. As seen in Figure 19, the elongation of the star profiles in the original image is emphasised by some filters and often causes false stars to be generated. This elongation is discussed in Errors. Whilst no particular filter appears to address all resolving issues, various different Wavelets yield important results. The final Wavelet shown in Figure 19, bottom right, locates the centres of stars particularly clearly and even resolves a binary star towards the top right corner of the frame. On the other hand, the grainy background is problematic when detecting stars automatically. The Full Width Wavelets perform well at adding definition to the stars though do not provide a clear position for each star. For detection purposes, the Full Width Wavelet with a Peak Width of 1 pixel was chosen as it provided a good compromise, did not emphasise elongation and allowed for reliable detection using the software described below.

FIG. 19: Application of different Wavelets to the initial image. From top left, clockwise: Full Width Filter with Peak width 1 pixel; Full Width Filter with Peak Width 2 pixels; Hat Width 10 pixels with Peak Width 4 pixels; Hat Width 20 pixels with Peak Width 2 pixels; Hat Width 60 with Peak Width 7; Hat Width 10 pixels with Peak Width 1 pixel. The size and definition of stellar objects can be seen to vary with changing filter parameters.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Star Detection

Due to the irregular PSF of FastCam stars, various star detection methods are made redundant. DAOFIND (a common user programme from the Image Reduction and Analysis Facility, IRAF,) for example, had a very low success rate in this case, with many false stars being detected and poor precision in locating the centroids of individual stars. Two separate star detection methods were considered and are discussed below. Results are discussed in Section III D.

1. SExtractor

Source Extractor, or SExtractor, is a versatile software tool designed for the automatic detection of stellar objects. It is built for speed rather than accuracy; a compromise, as it was intended for use on vast or crowded fields. It works by first determining and subtracting the background, filtering the image, then detecting objects above a specified threshold. The objects are subsequently deblended and a calculation is made of their magnitude. A catalogue is generated containing user specified parameters; in our case, position and magnitude.

2. StarFinder

StarFinder works along the same lines as IRAF's DAOPHOT package for crowded fields. The advantage of StarFinder is that, unlike DAOPHOT, an empirical PSF is created from the image for object detection. In our case, as there was no background information available, noise and background were also calculated from the image. A PSF is constructed using stars selected by the user, neighbouring stars are removed from each of these reference stars, and they are combined to form a variable profile. StarFinder subsequently looks for objects which fit the profile and subtracts them, exposing more objects. In this way a catalogue is generated, providing pixel coordinates and flux with their corresponding errors. This star detection method was adopted and was run on each field with a 3σ detection threshold. StarFinder was selected to provide both stellar coordinates and photometric values based on a trial study discussed in Section III D.

B. Astronomic Calibration

To convert between pixel and world coordinate systems, a polynomial transformation is found and implemented. The world coordinate system is that used by astronomers as a standard grid system for the location of stellar objects. It is the astronomic equivalent of latitude and longitude with axes termed Right Ascension and Declination. Right Ascension, RA, is measured in hours, minutes and seconds. If an object is directly overhead with RA 13:30:21.4, one hour later an object with RA 14:30:21.4 will be directly overhead. The right ascension of the sun on the vernal equinox, the 21st of March, is taken to be the zero point. Declination is measured in degrees, arcminutes and arcseconds and dictates the angular location with respect to the celestial equator. Declination can tell you how high an object will rise, by comparison with your location. By having this common coordinate system, all astronomic data can be easily shared around the globe.

The transformation can be described via the following polynomials

$$\Delta R.A. = a + b\Delta x + c\Delta y + d(\Delta x)^2 + e(\Delta y)^2 + f\Delta x\Delta y \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta Dec = g + h\Delta x + i\Delta y + j(\Delta x)^2 + k(\Delta y)^2 + l\Delta x\Delta y \quad (11)$$

where a to l represent constants defined by the particular image transformation, $\Delta R.A. = R.A. - R.A._{reference}$, $\Delta Dec = Dec - Dec_{reference}$, $\Delta x = x - x_{centre}$ and $\Delta y = y - y_{centre}$. The transformations here were generated using CCMAP from the IRAF. By providing an input list of reference stars in RA and DEC matched to stars detected in the image in pixel coordinates, CCMAP can generate the new coordinate system and apply it to the image. The reference R.A and Dec are determined as the mean of the input R.A. and Dec coordinates whilst the x_{centre} and y_{centre} are the geometric centre of the image. CCMAP provides the option of specifying the order of the polynomial, among other parameters. It was chosen to

generate the fit for the FastCam images using a projection in the tangent, or gnomonic, plane. Gnomonic projection is a variety of spherical mapping and displays great circles as straight lines¹³. It is commonly used in optical astronomy as well as traditional cartography.

It can be assumed that, over a relatively short time period, there will be stationary members of a Globular Cluster. A further assumption is that members which demonstrate large movement will be largely random and will not show a dominant direction of motion. This is exploited in the following method where a large amount of stars are used for an initial calibration and stars deviating greatly from the fit are subsequently removed in iterations. In this case, objects with a deviation greater than 1.8σ are rejected, where σ is the standard deviation of all points from the fit. By following this method, only stationary stars, or those with minimal motion, are used to produce the transformation. Figure 20 shows the user interface of CCMAP. Stars excluded from the fit are shown as circles surrounding crosses.

FIG. 20: CCMAP software, showing rejected objects and those forming the final transformation. Rejected objects are those with a circular marker. Objects which deviate by more than 1.8 times the root mean square are excluded.

Following the assignment of the world coordinate system, stellar positions can be calculated using the pixel coordinates produced by StarFinder and SExtractor. Via this method, the stars detected using FastCam can be compared to those in pre-existing catalogues.

1. Plate Calibration in the NOT

Field	Telescope	Stars Used	X Scale	Y Scale	Difference	Average Scale	Error	RMS	Size
1	NOT	33	0.030992	0.031102	-0.000110	0.031047	6.8E-005	0.00037	12.48
2	NOT	28	0.031111	0.030970	0.000141	0.031040	6.8E-005	0.00051	12.48
3	NOT	37	0.030999	0.031058	-5.8E-005	0.031029	6.8E-005	0.00032	12.47
4	NOT	16	0.031142	0.030995	0.000147	0.031069	6.8E-005	0.00040	12.49
5	NOT	9	0.030955	0.031101	-0.000146	0.031028	6.8E-005	0.00029	12.47
6	NOT	17	0.031365	0.031207	0.000158	0.031286	0.000112	0.00037	12.58
7	NOT	7	0.031153	0.031897	-0.000744	0.031525	0.000526	0.00051	12.67
9	NOT	16	0.031363	0.032088	-0.000726	0.031726	0.000513	0.00018	12.75

TABLE II: Table of plate scales and errors for all nine stellar fields. All units arcseconds. RMS is the root mean square, in arcseconds, of star deviations from the fit. Size is the edge length of the cropped field. All values in arcseconds. The first five fields, which were well calibrated with the Guhathakurta's Catalogue are combined to calculate an error value, the standard deviation of the X and Y plate scales for all five. The remaining four fields are assigned individual error values.

Each field was calibrated astrometrically, using a pixel list of stars provided by StarFinder matched with members of Guhathakurta's Catalogue, providing a plate scale (the ratio of arcseconds to pixels,) and rotation for each axis, x and y . Each image was originally 512 x 512 pixels, after removing a 55 pixel border we were left with 402 x 402 pixels. The x and y axes of the image should theoretically have the same plate scale, hence, by comparing the x and y plate scales generated by CCMAP in the astrometric calibration, an error on the plate scale can be found. Table II shows astrometric results for all fields including plate scales and errors. Only five of the stellar fields coincides entirely with Guhathakurta's Catalogue of 1992; out of the others, Fields 6 and 7 are partially covered and Fields 8 (discussed below) and 9 fall well outside. Those covered by the Catalogue were calibrated directly with its members whilst those outlying Fields were subsequently calibrated with the central Fields. Each Field was processed using a 3σ threshold to detect stars the results of which are seen in Table III. By comparison with Figure 17 it can be seen that the star density decreases with distance from the centre of Globular Cluster M3, located in Field 1.

Field	Stars Detected	In Region	Match at 0.1"	Match at 0.05"	Percentage in 0.1"	Match
1	82	82	79	22	96.3	
2	70	56	64	30	91.4	
3	85	85	66	62	77.6	
4	36	36	35	35	97.2	
5	37	37	30	23	81.0	
6	40	31	30	18	96.8	
7	39	13	11	7	86.4	
9	17	0	0	0	0	

TABLE III: Detected and matched stars for all four fields. Column 3 shows number of stars in region covered by Guhathakurta's Catalogue, to which we are comparing star positions. Fields 1 to 7 and 9 use stars detected by StarFinder. Columns 4 and 5 show the number of stars matched to those in Guhathakurta's Catalogue within a particular number of arcseconds. Column six shows the percentage of FastCam stars matched to Guhathakurta stars within 0.1" for each field.

2. Plate Calibration in the WHT

Field	Telescope	Stars Used	X Scale	Y Scale	Difference	Average Scale (")	Error (")	RMS (")	Size (")
8	WHT	10	0.018557	0.019071	-0.000514	0.018814	0.000363	0.000669	7.56

TABLE IV: Plate Scale values for Field 8. The comparatively small field of view is in accordance with the lower scale of arcseconds per pixel.

As seen in Table IV, the plate scale in the WHT is much lower than that in the NOT. The field of view from the WHT is smaller, reflecting the theoretically higher angular resolution which could be achieved using this method. The stars detected in this field were calibrated astrometrically and photometrically with other FastCam stars which had previously been calibrated with Guhathakurta’s Catalogue, making use of the overlap of the nine FastCam fields, see Image 17. The plate scale for WHT images had previously only been calculated previously using images of binary star systems. By calibrating this dense field imaged with FastCam in the WHT it is hoped to achieve a higher precision due to the increased number of input members in the coordinate transformation. Due to the poor image quality, an error of ± 0.3 milliarcseconds was calculated. A continuation of Table III is included below in Table V. 10 Stars were detected in total and none are found within the overlap region of the catalogues.

Field Stars Detected In Region		Match at 0.1"	Match at 0.05"	Percentage in 0.1"	Match
8	10	0	0	0	0

TABLE V: Data for Field 8, taken in the WHT. This field was not covered by Guhathakurta’s Catalogue.

C. Astrometric Accuracy

There are two sources of error in the location of the stars. Firstly, the precise allocation of the centroid coordinates introduces a sometimes large error. This error is inversely proportional to the magnitude of the star. The brightest stars may have a value as low as 0.1 milliarcseconds whilst the faintest may be displaced by up to 30 milliarcseconds, approximately a pixel. This error stems from our star detection programme, StarFinder, when trying to fit the empirical PSF to star candidates. The exact star profile of each source may vary from the PSF model introducing uncertainty in the fit. Faint sources prove to be poorer fits to the PSF, due to a lack of flux, hence carrying larger uncertainty on their exact position.

The second source of error stems from the transformation from pixel to world (RA and Dec.) coordinates. A root mean square (RMS) deviance of all calibration sources to the fit is calculated, reflecting the fact that the fit is imperfect. This value can be said to reflect further uncertainty in the world coordinates of a source and is constant across the whole field. See Table II for values of RMS for each field. The mean value across all fields is 0.4 milliarcseconds.

By adding these two errors together a unique error value in arcseconds was calculated for each star in our FastCam Catalogue ranging from tens to fractions of arcseconds. The brightest stars show the most certainty in their positions whilst the fainter stars carry a larger error. These values were used to define stellar movement as discussed in Section IV E on Stellar Movement and range from a fraction of a milliarcsecond to tens of milliarcseconds according to magnitude.

D. Photometric Calibration

Using the magnitudes calculated by StarFinder or SExtractor and Guhathakurta’s catalogue from 1992, the images were calibrated photometrically. To test the capability of the photometry of our star detection options, a trial calibration was made with Field 3. A match was done, comparing the reference catalogue with the outputs of StarFinder and SExtractor and each star with a match was selected for calibration. A fit was calculated for each field, and iterated to remove any outliers. This fit transformed between the generated flux (or magnitude,) values outputted by the methods and the I Mag data from Guhathakurta’s Catalogue. The final transformation was applied to all stellar fluxes to give a new magnitude value. The new magnitude was compared to that of Guhathakurta’s Catalogue, generating an estimate of the error. Whilst many of these differences may indeed reflect errors, it must be remembered that M3 is home to a large number of variable stars. Hence, it is likely that any clear outliers fall into this category. Figures 21 and 22 show the difference in I Mag, compared to that of Guhathakurta, with decreasing stellar magnitude. Errors, differences between FastCam magnitudes and those of Guhathakurta, tend to be greater at lower magnitudes though very bright stars also show a high error.

FIG. 21: FastCam I Magnitude generated via StarFinder compared to I Magnitude from Guhathakurta. Average absolute error, 0.127 stellar magnitudes.

FIG. 22: FastCam I Magnitude generated via SExtractor compared to I magnitude from Guhathakurta. Average absolute error, 0.387 mag.

Clearly, SExtractor, as seen in Figure 22, having an average error of 0.39 mag, is a less accurate method by which to determine stellar magnitudes. StarFinder, with an average error of 0.13, yields more credible values. Whilst SExtractor appears to provide reasonable astrometric results, less confidence is to be taken in its photometry. Figure 23 shows three histograms portraying magnitude distribution; StarFinder and SExtractor magnitudes are shown with Guhathakurta magnitudes provided for comparison.

StarFinder was chosen to provide the photometric and astrometric information for all fields, from the NOT and WHT alike, using images filtered with a Mexican Hat of a central width of 1 pixel. A detection threshold of 3σ was chosen to limit false detections. The output star list for each field was used to calibrate each field astrometrically and photometrically, creating a new catalogue of M3 in the I-band. During the photometric calibration, stars with magnitude dimmer than 16 were excluded from the transformation as fainter stars are more likely to have an inaccurate magnitude in Guhathakurta's Catalogue. Any stars which appeared in multiple FastCam pointings were averaged and included as a unique catalogue member. This catalogue is included in Appendix A of this report.

FIG. 23: Stellar magnitudes, generated by SExtractor, StarFinder and from Guhathakurta's Catalogue 1992. Field 3, centred on 13:42:11.269, +28:22:35.42. Guhathakurta's Catalog includes much fainter stars which have been excluded for comparative purposes; clearly StarFinder is a far similar fit than SExtractor. Guhathakurta's Catalogue contains 85 stars with magnitude greater than 17, StarFinder's, 103 and SExtractor's, 86.

E. Photometric Accuracy

To evaluate the potential error of our method, the I magnitudes calculated from FastCam were compared to those obtained by Guhathakurta from the Hubble Space Telescope (HST). Only data from the NOT is considered here as the WHT falls outside the catalogue. Since the image from the HST is considered to be of highest possible quality, by comparing our values with those in Guhathakurta's Catalogue it should be possible to obtain an approximation of the absolute error. A measurement of the difference in I Mag was obtained by subtracting the FastCam I Mag from that of Guhathakurta. The distribution of the errors is shown in Figure 24. The median of this data was evaluated at -0.01950 and the mean, at 0.01895, reflecting the positive skew seen in the data.

FIG. 24: Error Distribution, FastCam I magnitude subtracted from that of Guhathakurta. Median -0.0195, Mean 0.0190.

When the errors are considered as a function of magnitude, the average error remains approximately constant between magnitudes 12 and 17. Figure 25 shows the development of error with magnitude. Blue represents the average error and pink, the average absolute error i.e. the average positive magnitude difference. Whilst the average error remains close to zero for all reliably sampled magnitude bins, the absolute error is somewhat higher, reflecting the typical deviance from Guhathakurta’s I Mag measurements. Generally, ground based imaging methods tend to overestimate stellar flux, this is similarly observed in our results. If only the well sampled magnitude bins are considered, those containing over 10 stars, the average absolute error is found to be 0.1172 Magnitudes. Details of bin membership is found in Table VI. When compared to Guhathakurta’s photometric error value of 0.1 mag, it can be presumed that FastCam photometric results are accurate to a similar degree. HST data yields an error of 0.1 mag due to the noisy background of the images; the telescope picks up flux from even the faintest stars leading to relatively large error in photometric results.

FIG. 25: Average Error as a function of magnitude. The blue line represents the average error and the pink, the average absolute error.

I Mag Band	Average I Error	Stars Used
11 - 12	0.1922	1
12 - 13	0.1446	6
13 - 14	0.1020	17
14 - 15	0.0950	30
15 - 16	0.1304	49
16 - 17	0.1094	85
17 - 18	0.1493	42
18 - 19	0.8570	8

TABLE VI: Average absolute I Mag errors, as compared with Guhathakurta, across the entire magnitude range. Also included is the number of stars used to produce this average in each magnitude bin.

As seen in Figure 17, several fields within our data have overlapping regions. This allows FastCam data to be compared with itself providing an estimate of this methods error. In this study a star from the database was considered to be the same as another star when their coordinates were within 0.05 arcseconds. 63 stars were found to be pairs whilst a further 8 were measured three times in separate FastCam pointings. It is possible that there are further sets of double or triple star detection but the threshold was set to within one pixel to avoid selecting close companions.

Star1	Star2	Star3	Average Flux	Standard Deviation
183	18	103	15.59	0.14
222	52	137	16.98	0.21
278	88	240	13.87	0.11
298	105	260	16.00	0.02
321	242	281	14.53	0.07
400	391	351	13.29	0.07
404	393	370	15.34	0.15
405	372	396	15.55	0.10

TABLE VII: Stars detected in three separate FastCam pointings.

Table VI shows the triple star measurements, including the three IDs from the FastCam Catalogue, the Average Flux and the Standard Deviation of the three flux values. Table VIII is a cut of the full 63 double star detections. The mean standard deviation of the triple detections is 0.1081 and of the double detections is 0.0911. By averaging these multiple entries, seen in Tables VI and VIII, in the FastCam Catalogue, a final catalogue was created with single entries for star candidates. Further multiple detections were filtered visually resulting in an I-band Catalogue of 332 objects. If an average of the triple star variation, double star variation and catalogue variation with respect to Guhathakurta's Catalogue is taken a value of 0.105 mag is obtained. Guhathakurta states his errors as 0.1 mag clearly indicating that these photometric values are comparable to a similar degree of accuracy. There was a minor difference between the filter used with FastCam and that used in the HST, the filters varied slightly in bandwidth and quantum efficiency, adding a further degree of imprecision though this is unquantifiable here and assumed to be negligible for the scope of this study.

Star1	Star2	Average Flux	Standard Deviation
94	6	14.88	0.21
101	17	15.58	0.17
108	25	16.01	0.13
153	1	11.85	0.05
154	84	12.21	0.21
158	2	13.42	0.08
160	3	13.74	0.04
161	4	13.94	0.09
175	7	14.83	0.04
179	98	15.39	0.18
190	21	15.86	0.05
191	19	15.84	0.11
194	23	15.94	0.06
199	30	16.14	0.06
200	127	16.56	0.47
202	35	16.29	0.02
205	33	16.30	0.12
210	124	16.67	0.22
217	39	16.57	0.10
219	38	16.58	0.16
220	40	16.60	0.14
224	46	16.75	0.04
225	43	16.73	0.09
226	50	16.80	0.01
236	70	17.42	0.20
246	96	14.96	0.16
251	95	15.08	0.01
256	102	15.75	0.01
266	113	16.33	0.07
273	116	16.67	0.05
274	83	11.50	0.21
276	238	13.02	0.03
277	85	13.17	0.11
282	243	14.59	0.01
284	245	14.69	0.03
287	249	15.05	0.01
288	248	15.03	0.04
290	252	15.19	0.06
292	254	15.40	0.02
293	255	15.68	0.04
294	257	15.81	0.05
296	264	16.01	0.14

TABLE VIII: Cut of list of stars detected in two separate FastCam pointings.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Angular Resolution

1. Angular Resolution in the NOT

Lucky Imaging has been found to generate diffraction or near diffraction limited images for stellar fields in previous studies, such as that of Labadie et al., 2010. To obtain an estimate of the angular resolution of the FastCam images analysed here, a study was made of the Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) value of the stellar profile. To evaluate the potential of Lucky Imaging with FastCam, Field 2 was chosen to provide the PSF since it showed the most circular form with least elongation. The PSF of Field 2 is shown in Figure 26. The original, unfiltered image is studied initially.

By calculating the FWHM, the angular resolution is effectively defined. Two close stars are said to be resolved when they are separated by their FWHM. Figure 27 shows two very close stars, thought to be a binary system, in Field 3 with a separation of $0.1844''$. When considering the approximate FWHM of the smallest stars, the Full Width Half Max of the gaussian core was considered. Taking an average of twenty stars across the field, a mean FWHM was calculated to be 4.9 pixels. When considered in arcseconds this gives us an angular resolution of $0.15''$. Our two close stars in Figure 27 are separated by a distance greater than this and are clearly resolved.

FIG. 26: Stellar Profile, PSF, in Field 2.

The theoretical diffraction limited angular resolution in the I-band of the Nordic Optical Telescope, used to observe Field 2, is approximately $0.075''$ and that of the WHT is $0.045''$. Whilst the angular resolution of the FastCam images is found to be 2.0 times larger than the theoretical limit, it is a clear improvement on that of a seeing limited image which in this case is over 7 times poorer.

FIG. 27: Distance between two close but resolved stars, a binary pair, in Field 3.

When considering the angular resolution of the filtered images, the FWHM calculated from NOT reaches $0.11''$ (approximately 3.4 pixels), getting close to the theoretical limit. These images can be said to have reached near diffraction limited resolution via a ground based imaging method, hence achieving one objective of the project. The values of Angular Resolution in Seeing Limited, Lucy Imaged and Filtered images can be found in Table 27 along with corresponding images.

FIG. 28: From left to right. FastCam image from the William Herschel Telescope of Field 8, stars are marked by blue squares. The same field but taken from the Hubble Space Telescope.

Lucky Imaging NOT	Filtered Image	Seeing Image
0.15'' Angular Resolution	0.11'' Angular Resolution	0.56'' Angular Resolution
2.0 × Theoretical Limit	1.4 × Theoretical Limit	7.5 × Theoretical Limit

TABLE IX: Angular Resolution for Lucky Image, Filtered Lucky Image and Seeing Image from the Nordic Optical Telescope.

2. Angular Resolution in the WHT

The WHT did not respond to the Lucky Imaging and filtering process with equal success due to lack of stellar definition. Consequently the FWHM fails to approach the diffraction limit. FastCam and Lucky Imaging has thus far been found to have more success when used in small telescopes. This is due to the higher probability of observing a period of low atmospheric dispersion across the entire field of view. As discussed in Section 1B, the atmosphere is composed of pockets of homogeneous air, with an average length of the Fried Parameter, through which incoming flux must pass, thereby being distorted and forming a speckle image on the detector. Conversely, a larger telescope would have a higher diffraction limited angular resolution which may be achieved with Lucky Imaging. A compromise must be made on desired angular resolution whilst taking the Fried Parameter into account.

Two fields were observed with FastCam from the WHT, one of which being the left hand image in Figure 28. The second field was of such low definition that it was not calibrated astrometrically. Locating the region within the cluster was not achievable. Figure 28 is composed of 7 cubes of data, out of a possible 10. When compared to the same region observed by the Hubble Space Telescope, right hand image of Figure 28, it is clear that only the brightest stars are detected. No external catalogue was found to cover this area of M3 in detail, Guhathakurta's catalogue only extends over a limited field, hence high precision evaluation of photometric results is currently unachievable.

Definition is slightly improved upon implementing a Wavelet, see left hand image of Figure 29, though

FIG. 29: From left to right. Filtered version of Figure 28; full width Mexican Hat Wavelet used with a peak size of 1 pixel. WHT field; stars detected by WHT shown as blue squares and those detected by NOT as purple circles.

any faint star candidates remain unclear. The seeing conditions were reported to be poor on the night of observations; Lucky Imaging has been found to improve resolution by a factor of 3-4 with poorer seeing conditions⁹ as observed in this case. When compared with the data covering the same field, but taken from NOT, see right hand image of Figure 29, the ratio of star detection can be calculated. 53% of stars detected with NOT were also detected by WHT. The WHT PSF had a visibly larger seeing disk than that of the NOT reflecting the higher atmospheric dispersion across the field of view. The FWHM of the FastCam image is evaluated at 10.1 pixels or $0.19''$. This is over four times the theoretical limit of $0.045''$. When the filtered image is examined for angular resolution, an improved value of $0.17''$ is obtained. Although these resolutions are an improvement of the seeing resolution, $0.23''$, the Lucky Imaging process fails to approach the diffraction limit in this case due to a lack of good seeing images within the data cubes. These values can be found in Table IV A 2. Surprisingly, more stars appear to be visible in the seeing image. This may be due, once again, to the scarcity of good seeing frames within the cubes, leading to a poor selection for the final image.

Lucky Imaging WHT	Filtered Image	Seeing Image
$0.19''$ Angular Resolution	$0.17''$ Angular Resolution	$0.40''$ Angular Resolution
$4.2 \times$ Theoretical Limit	$3.7 \times$ Theoretical Limit	$8.9 \times$ Theoretical Limit

TABLE X: Angular Resolution for Lucky Image, Filtered Lucky Image and Seeing Image from the William Herschel Telescope.

B. Unmatched Objects

We present a catalogue of unmatched objects for one central field, Field 3, in Table XI. Figure 3 was chosen as, being the densest field, it has most to benefit from FastCam's resolving power; close companion stars may be detected in this Field which went unrecorded in Guhathakurta's Catalogue. These objects are defined as those failing to match a star from Guhathakurta's Catalogue within 0.1 arcseconds and are shown in Figure 30 and

clear errors have been removed after visual inspection. Stars may fail to match for a variety of reasons; a star may have moved beyond $0.1''$ from its original position, it may be too dim to have been detected previously, it may be a variable star and has been observed here with a higher magnitude or it may be a close companion to a bright star and as such was unresolved in previous methods. It is also possible that the star is a false detection within the FastCam image. A three sigma threshold was used to detect stars, reducing the chance of a false detection due to background noise. Nevertheless, each potential new star candidate was visually analysed and categorised.

Number	RA	DEC	Intensity	Suspected Reason for Unmatched Object
1	13:42:11.589	+28:22:35.25	14.28	Large Movement
2	13:42:11.454	+28:22:37.42	14.39	Binary System
3	13:42:11.241	+28:22:37.12	15.18	Large Shift
4	13:42:11.329	+28:22:33.60	15.62	Close Companion
5	13:42:11.130	+28:22:34.41	15.94	Close Companion
6	13:42:11.436	+28:22:32.56	16.37	New Bright Star
7	13:42:11.514	+28:22:41.43	16.40	Possible Error
8	13:42:10.888	+28:22:33.17	16.67	New Faint Star
9	13:42:11.341	+28:22:35.05	17.01	New Bright Star
10	13:42:10.955	+28:22:38.39	17.03	New Faint Star
11	13:42:11.493	+28:22:40.23	17.30	New Faint Star
12	13:42:11.565	+28:22:35.83	17.21	Large Movement

TABLE XI: Unmatched Stars in Field 3.

FIG. 30: Unmatched Stars in Field 3, circled in red. The centre of the image is at 13:42:11.269, +28:22:35.42 with RA increasing upwards and Dec increasing towards the right with a plate scale of $0.031''$.

Over the central four fields, 7 stars were considered to be definite new stars, i.e. well defined stars without a counterpart in Guhathakurta's Catalogue. This excluded possible errors and large movement candidates.

RA	Dec	I mag
13:42:10.955	+28:22:52.95	15.38
13:42:11.702	+28:22:50.46	16.91
13:42:11.846	+28:22:49.31	17.75
13:42:12.023	+28:22:49.58	17.15
13:42:11.454	+28:22:37.42	14.39
13:42:11.130	+28:22:34.41	15.94
13:42:10.955	+28:22:38.39	17.03

TABLE XII: Newly detected stars in Fields 1 - 4 taken from the Nordic Optical Telescope.

C. Photometric Results

Studying the relative colours and luminosities of Globular Cluster members can provide much useful information about the cluster itself. A Globular Cluster is formed when a large cloud of dust collapses, giving birth to thousands of stars. Hertzsprung Russell diagrams give an indication of the age of the cluster. This is due to two key points; firstly, that all stars contained in the diagram are the same age and secondly that they are at the same distance meaning that brighter stars are truly more luminous rather than simply being situated closer to the detector. Hertzsprung Russell diagrams plot temperature, spectral type or colour against luminosity, absolute magnitude or apparent magnitude. Apparent magnitude can only be used as the Y axis if all stars are at the same distance, which in our case is true thereby simplifying the analysis process.

Hertzsprung Russell diagrams of Globular Clusters show turn-off points along the main sequence. The brightest stars, those at the bluest end of the spectrum, have already died and moved to other points within the diagram, causing an abrupt change of direction in the main sequence. By analysing the limiting temperature and luminosity of this turnoff, the age of a cluster can be approximated. For example, if all main sequence stars which would only burn for fewer than 4 million years no longer appear on the HR diagram, the cluster can be said to have an estimated age of 4 million years. Figure 31 shows the HR diagram for M3 with a turn off clearly visible on the main sequence.

Some objects of particular interest in Globular Clusters are Blue Stragglers. These are the few stars which appear after the main sequence turnoff in Figure 31, therefore having an apparent age higher than that of the cluster itself. As discussed above in the introduction, there are various theories as to the origins of these stars.

FIG. 31: Hertzsprung Russell Diagram, M3, main sequence turn-off can be seen in the centre of the diagram with the Blue Stragglers trailing behind.

The I magnitudes generated by FastCam can be compared to the V and U magnitudes calculated by Guhathakurta in his Catalogue of M3 from 1992 thereby providing a relative temperature scale for use as the x axis. Here the FastCam I magnitude has been plotted against the U magnitude from Guhathakurta minus the V magnitude, Figure 33. Similarly, V from Guhathakurta has been plotted against U from Guhathakurta minus I from FastCam, Figure 34. This second colour magnitude diagram affords a longer colour baseline resulting in a clearer definition of different star groups. It shows clearly the location of the Blue Straggler candidates and the location of RR Lyraes. As we only have flux information in the I-band, it is impossible to assign our stars a certain stellar type; their V and U magnitudes may also have changed, since Guhathakurta's Catalogue was made, which would affect their position on the Colour Magnitude Diagram. However, previously classified stars have been located within the data and are shown for reference. Guhathakurta plotted a similar graph during his analysis of M3 using data from the HST, seen in Figure 32, and marks the region in which stars were considered to be Blue Stragglers.

FIG. 32: Guhathakurta's Colour Magnitude Diagram of V vs U-I, showing location of Blue Stragglers.

The known Blue Stragglers have been plotted separately in Figures 33 and 34, falling just behind the main sequence turn-off. The stars with I magnitudes varying by more than 0.4 stellar magnitudes from those calculated by Guhathakurta are also shown. These stars with large magnitude differences could be due to a number of reasons. The star could be faint; as seen from the average error table, Table VI, the dimmer stars have less precise magnitude measurements when using this method. The star could be a Variable Star, thereby showing a different magnitude than that measured in previous studies when it may have been at a different point of its luminosity cycle. The flux could be combined with that of a close companion, in either FastCam data or the HST data used by Guhathakurta, causing a large measured magnitude difference. Table XIII shows a list of stars with large magnitude difference in the central region, all taken from data from NOT on the 28th of May, along with a likely reason for the result.

The vast majority of these stars with a large magnitude difference fall low down on the CMD. Intrinsically, there is a greater chance of error in magnitude calculation for dimmer stars, hence these large magnitude differences are likely to be a product of this error. Two of these stars do, however, match up with stars previously reported to be RR Lyrae variables. These are made clear in Table XIII and are shown as green diamonds surrounding red asterisks in Figures 33 and 34.

Guhathakurta ID	Guhathakurta I Mag	FastCam ID	FastCam I Mag	Likely Reason
109	18.55	380	16.02	Faint
158	15.31	323	14.89	Known Variable
539	16.06	214	16.60	Close Companion
856	17.61	230	16.93	Faint
980	18.51	233	17.05	Faint
1462	18.03	147	17.56	Faint
1571	16.61	54	17.04	Faint
1600	15.42	8	14.95	Known Variable
1632	17.9	66	17.47	Faint
1709	18.66	81	18.00	Close Companion
1989	17.99	67	17.48	Faint
2054	18.23	72	17.62	Faint

TABLE XIII: Stars with large magnitude difference when compared to Guhathakurta's catalogue

FIG. 33: Colour Magnitude Diagram, I vs U-V magnitudes. Blue squares show Blue Stragglers, green show known RR Lyrae Stars from Christine Clement's Variable Catalogue of M3, pink show RR Lyraes from Guhathakurta's Catalogue whilst red asterisks show stars found to vary by 0.4 stellar magnitudes from Guhathakurta's values.

FIG. 34: Colour Magnitude Diagram, V vs U-I magnitudes. Blue squares show Blue Stragglers, green show known RR Lyrae Stars from Christine Clement's Variable Catalogue of M3, pink show RR Lyraes from Guhathakurta's Catalogue whilst red asterisks show stars found to vary by 0.4 stellar magnitudes from Guhathakurta's values. 0.4 chosen as representative of the 3σ threshold.

D. Completeness

When the I magnitudes of all stars in our FastCam Catalogue are represented on a bar chart, approximation can be made as to its completeness. The completeness indicates the magnitude up to which all stars are included in the catalogue. Beyond this value, the probability of a star being contained in the catalogue decreases. Figure 35 shows the I magnitudes for the FastCam Catalogue and for Guhathakurta's Catalogue. Guhathakurta's Catalogue, made with data from the Hubble Space Telescope, is clearly more complete, including all stars with magnitude greater than 18.5. FastCam's Catalogue is complete to approximately 16.2 mag. This is predominantly due to the differences in exposure times of each field, as can be seen in Table 17. The HST image has an exposure time of 10.2 minutes whereas the longest exposure time of any FastCam image is under 1.1 minutes. The quality of the images also defines the catalogue completeness as close or faint stars will only be detected in images of good angular resolution.

FIG. 35: I magnitudes in FastCam and Guhathakurta Catalogues. FastCam's Catalogue is complete to $\simeq 16.2$ and Guhathakurta's to $\simeq 18.5$ Stellar magnitudes.

Previous studies with FastCam data have achieved catalogues complete up to 19 mag though their images were constructed with several hundred cubes of 1000 frames of data. Since several of our Fields had as few as 10 cubes of data, an overall completeness up to 16.2 is commendable. When Field 1 is considered in isolation, it is seen that it is complete for magnitudes up to 17.5. This field is made up of 31 cubes, reflecting the higher sensitivity. Figure 36 shows the completeness of Field 1. In contrast, Field 3 consists of 7 cubes and yields a catalogue complete to magnitude 16.7. Figure 37 shows the magnitude distribution for Field 3. 14.7s of integration time is the lowest value for any field, indicating that an overall catalogue completeness up to 16.2 is a conservative estimate.

FIG. 36: Magnitudes of Field 1. Complete to 17.5 mag.

FIG. 37: Magnitudes of Field 3. Complete to 16.7 mag.

E. Stellar Movement

The internal dynamics of Globular Clusters is of high scientific interest. Advances in resolving power have made it possible to track the motion of individual stars in dense fields over periods as short as a few years. The core of Omega Centauri, a large, bright cluster orbiting the Milky Way, has been studied by comparing two HST images taken with a four year separation. The stellar movement in this time period was calculated and extrapolated to map the motion over the next 10,000 years²⁸. By comparing FastCam data with that gathered by Guhathakurta in 1992⁴, it is hoped to evaluate the potential of making a similar study using data from Lucky Imaging.

A unique uncertainty value for stellar coordinates is generated for each star candidate, see Section III C, by combining the error in detection and the calibration error. The magnitude of this error value is inversely proportional to the brightness of the star; bright stars have little uncertainty in their position whilst faint stars can have up to $0.8''$ of positional error. Observed movement, the difference between FastCam and Guhathakurta coordinates, below this value is not considered to represent true motion and is excluded from the study.

Figure 38 shows Fields 1 to 4 with star movement superimposed. The quality of data from the WHT was insufficient for a similar study to be made. The movements were calculated for each separate field and later plotted on the combination of all four central fields. The circles represent stellar positions as detected by Guhathakurta whilst the arrow, scaled by 25, points towards the location in our FastCam image. The centre of the field was estimated to be at, $13:42:11.585 +28:22:33.44$ and results are shown relative to these coordinates. The centre of M3, as determined by Shawl and White 1986, is shown as the dark cross towards the lower left corner.

Of particular interest are the stars flagged as showing movement in multiple FastCam pointings. These are identified as single circles with multiple arrows. Figure 39 shows a zoom of the very centre of the image where there is an example of a star showing large movement in two separate pointings. Although the respective movements do have a slight angular separation, they are approximately in the same direction clearly indicating real motion. This separation is due to the method's error with respect to itself. It must also be remembered that the motion is scaled by 25, emphasising any error in the FastCam position.

FIG. 38: Fields 1 to 4 with scaled movements ($\times 25$) superimposed. Green circles represents position in Guhathakurta's Catalogue with arrow pointing in direction of stars identified in FastCam images. Dark cross shows the approximate centre as estimated for this study.

FIG. 39: A zoom of the centre of Figure 38. Blue crosses mark the positions of stars in Guhathakurta's Catalogue generated with data from 1992. The two arrows emanating from the same star show stellar movement in approximately the same direction (stars detected in two separate fields,) with the exaggerated angular separation due to a scaling of factor 25.

Movement of stars at the very edge of fields is excluded due to the increased likelihood of imprecise location. If only part of the PSF is featured in the image, the location of the centroid carries a far greater error. One particular star showed an movement of over 12 milliarcseconds per year which is very unlikely to be a genuine value. The average movement per year across the entire field, in milliarcseconds,

was calculated to be 1.99. Converted to kilometres per second this motion is evaluated at 97.28 km/s. Figure 40 shows the distribution of movement magnitudes for all stars excluding those on the edge of fields showing anomalously large movement. This carries the assumption that movement is linear and parallel to the plane of view whereas in reality the stars are more likely to be travelling along curved paths or at an angle.

FIG. 40: Average movements in central Fields in km/s. Stars from field edges exhibiting large motion are excluded.

When the average movement is considered as a function of distance from the centre of the cluster, some little insight can be gained into the internal dynamics of the Cluster. Figure 41 shows the average proper motion in rings of 1.24 arcseconds in diameter around the point assumed to be the centre. As found in a similar study made by McNamara on M15²⁷, there appears to be a decrease in average velocity with distance, the trend becoming less linear with distance. More information can be gained by studying the dispersion of this internal motion within the same rings. Figure 42 demonstrates the dispersion. By analysing this curve it is possible to make an estimate of the mass of a central body; if the motion a point indicates the presence of a mass far greater than the stellar mass contained within the distance being examined a black hole is a likely candidate for a central body.

FIG. 41: Average Velocity with distance from centre of M3. Stars have been considered in consecutive rings of width 1.24 arcseconds in each of which an average yearly motion has been calculated.

FIG. 42: Velocity Dispersion with distance from centre of M3. Again, stars have been considered in rings of 1.24 arcseconds about the centre.

The imprecision in stellar coordinates due to the uncertainty in centroid coordinates leads to a substantial error in this proper motion. This error is related to the magnitude of the star, as seen in Figure 43, with brighter stars having more precise coordinates than fainter stars. For stars brighter than 16 mag the mean error due to imprecision in detection in FastCam is 16.8 km/s and for those fainter than 16 mag, 23.2 km/s. A further error in these movement values is that from star detection in Guhathakurta's Catalogue. Since the HST images used to create this catalogue had a much longer exposure time, the location of the centroids should carry a smaller error due to the improved PSF fit achieved with greater flux. A reasonable assumption is that Guhathakurta achieves an astrometric accuracy twice that found in this study. Taking this error into account, the average proper motion for bright stars is 91.8 ± 25.2 km/s and that of faint stars, 107.5 ± 34.8 km/s.

FIG. 43: Error from FastCam in star movement related to magnitude. Faint stars display larger error.

F. Blue Straggler Evaluation

Three Blue Stragglers were located within our nine calibrated fields of data. Of these, only one was sufficiently bright for a study of its flux over time to be carried out. This star is located at 13:42:11.51 +28:22:30.1 and has a magnitude of 16.64 in Guhathakurta's Catalogue and 16.77 in the FastCam Catalogue. Flux over time can be studied by performing individual photometric analysis on each individual cube taken of a field. Each cube is composed of 1000 frames, each frame lasting 30ms. A few seconds were taken between each cube for FastCam to be reset. The combination of run time and this brief pause between each cube gives an approximate length of 35 seconds for each cube. Fields 1 and 3 contain our target Blue Straggler and Field 3 was chosen for the study. Since the star is one of the faintest detected in the image, the cubes were grouped in pairs to facilitate detection and limit error on flux measurements. Each pair of cubes was combined into a single image using the shift-and-add routine and photometry was performed using StarFinder. In this way, 14 chronological images were made. Cubes 10 and 11 are not present in the data resulting in the gap in Figures 44 and 45 below. Figure 44 shows the flux of the Blue Straggler through time along with an average flux and the flux of a bright test star included for comparison. Refer to Table XIV for definitions of the four data series plotted in Figures 44 and 45.

Flux	Mean Flux Colour in Diagrams	
Blue Straggler	3.01	Blue
10 Star Average	64.6	Black
Bright Test Star	132.2	Green
Weak Test Star	24.8	Pink

TABLE XIV: Mean flux for each set of data shown in Figures 44 and 45.

An important consideration when measuring the change in flux through time is the possibility that each image may produce different flux values for all stars. To remove this effect a mean of the flux from several stars was subtracted from the flux of the Blue Straggler for each image. The normalised mean flux, calculated from 10 stars, was multiplied by the average of the data series, i.e. the Blue Straggler or a test star, being analysed and was subsequently subtracted from said data series giving a value of the absolute deviation. It was assumed that the stars used to form this mean had stable magnitudes though this is unknown; to attempt to negate the possibility of a variable star affecting results the average was taken of 10 reasonably bright stars, i.e. with magnitude brighter than 15. Figure 45 shows the deviation of the Blue Straggler from the mean through time.

FIG. 44: Normalised change in flux of Blue Straggler through time; blue represents the Blue Straggler, black represents the average flux of ten stars, green represents the flux of a bright test star and pink represents the flux of a weak test star. The flux of each data series is normalised, i.e. divided by its own average. Clearly, the Blue Straggler can be seen to deviate though this may not reflect true change in flux. There is a break in the graph at 5 minutes due to a lack of data.

FIG. 45: Absolute variation of flux with time; blue represents Blue Straggler, green represents a bright test star and pink represents a weak test star. Bright test star clearly has largest absolute variation though Blue Straggler shows large variation for its low magnitude.

As expected, the bright test star shows a large absolute variation though this is negligible compared to its magnitude. The weak star demonstrates little flux variation in accordance with its lower magnitude. An even weaker star would be expected to show yet smaller absolute variation though this is not the case when analysing the Blue Straggler. Although a clear variation in the Blue Straggler is observed, it cannot be said to represent the true change in flux. The change in flux is of the same order as the flux of the star itself. It seems that either the errors for this faint star prohibit reliable analysis, or that this method is insufficient for such a precise study. The star itself is very faint, even more so in images made with only two cubes. Consequently, in images with poorer seeing, it is not clearly defined. So much so that a 1σ detection threshold had to be used in the photometry for the star to be detected at all as opposed to the usual 3σ threshold. A brighter star should respond with more success to this method of detecting variations through time although Blue Stragglers are probably not possible candidates due to their typically low magnitude.

V. ERRONEOUS ELONGATION AND CATALOGUE MATCHING

Cube	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Elongation	2	9	9	9	9	9	8	8	8	4	-	-	7	7	2	4	3	6	6	7	7	7	2	2	1	2	6	4	1	4	1	2

TABLE XV: Elongation observed in each cube from Field 3. 1 denotes circular PSF whilst 10 indicates extreme elongation, - indicates missing cube.

Anomalous elongation was observed over various cubes of FastCam data, the behaviour is most pronounced in Field 3, see Figure 46. Previous fields observed during the same night by FastCam do not show this trait, nor do subsequent data sets. It is thought that this could be due to a focusing problem which was resolved

upon adjustment of the telescope. However, there is evidence suggesting that it is due to other reasons. If all of the 32 cubes of data from Field 3 are considered separately, the change in elongation through time can be observed. There appears to be no obvious improvement or deterioration with time, some of the most circular cubes are isolated within cubes showing large asymmetry. See Table XV for details of elongation in separate, chronological cubes.

It is possible that the atmospheric dynamics themselves have caused this effect, with a higher probability of speckle occurrence along a particular axis, though this is unknown. A wind of 10m/s was recorded in the observations in the NOT on the 28th of May, coinciding with the images displaying most pronounced elongation. To minimise the problem of elongation, only cubes exhibiting reasonably circular stellar profiles were included to make the final image of the field. In this case, cubes with an elongation of 4 or less (Table XV,) were included.

A further difficulty was encountered when trying to cross match our FastCam Catalogue with those of others. Generally within M3 there appears to be a lack of a uniform astronomic calibration meaning that when superposing catalogues, objects fail to match up. This was true for each catalogue examined. In some cases our FastCam Catalogue was recalibrated to enable comparison but in others this was impossible due to low numbers of catalogue members. Consequently, identifying pulsar candidates, among others, was not achievable.

FIG. 46: Elongation seen in various cubes, primarily in Field 3. Seen here, Cube 1 of Field 3.

VI. CONTINUATION AND SUGGESTIONS

One of the main limitations of this study was the amount of data; here, the catalogue completeness was limited to 16.2 whereas studies with several hundred cubes have achieved catalogues complete to magnitude 19. Additional cubes of data would also facilitate a more thorough study of flux through time. The periods of variable stars may be observable if data were taken over several hours instead of the 20 minutes available here for analysis. Ensuring good focus in the camera may also help to eliminate the problem of elongation observed over various fields.

To be able to assign a stellar population to a given star, its magnitude must be calculated using several filters. In this report we have only I-band data which was paired with V and U data from a pre-existing catalogue to create Colour Magnitude Diagrams. As this data was from two different years, with a 16 year gap, it was not truly representative of either. To make an accurate Colour Magnitude Diagram, data from several filters must be taken at more or less the same time. Hence, FastCam should be used with multiple filters. The difficulty is that Lucky Imaging works more effectively in the I-band, as seeing is better at longer wavelengths, making obtaining good data in other optical bands difficult.

To continue the movement study, new data could be taken at the end of this decade and compared with both our catalogue and that of Guhathakurta. Coherent movement observed across these three images would confirm that this method is reliable and may yield answers as to the internal dynamics of M3. Given time, the current study could be extended by making a precise study of movement in relation to the centre of the cluster. A vector to each star could be compared to the vector of motion, facilitating the analysis of the angular displacement between the two vectors thereby indicating the direction of motion from the frame of reference of the centre. Although the overall averages of movement in RA and Dec in Figure 38 is approximately 0, this gives little indication as to the internal dynamics with respect to the centre and a full analysis should be made to detect possible rotation or contraction.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

As seen in this report, Lucky Imaging with FastCam offers an accurate method for dense field analysis. A stellar catalogue was created using the method in the core of Globular Cluster M3. This catalogue contains over 330 stars, with a mean photometric error of 0.117 mag, and is complete to magnitude 16.2. By comparing our data to a pre-existing catalogue made by Guhathakurta, it was seen that all stars with magnitude brighter than this completeness value were detected. In the very densest regions of the cluster, a density of 0.54 stars per square arcsecond was recorded for stars brighter than 16.2 mag. Colour Magnitude Diagrams were constructed by combining FastCam data with that from Guhathakurta's Catalogue and known Blue Stragglers and Variable Stars were located. A new binary was detected at 13:42:11.45 +22:28:37.4 which was previously unresolved in HST images. A total of 7 new stars were identified within the FastCam images which do not feature in Guhathakurta's Catalogue. These fall within the central four fields studied where there is a complete overlap of the two catalogues.

Data was collected in the 2.5m Northern Optical Telescope (NOT) and the 4.2m William Herschel Telescope (WHT), both found in Roque de los Muchachos, Spain. This data was processed using a 7% selection threshold and convolved with a Mexican Hat Wavelet filter to add definition. An angular resolution of 0.11" was achieved in the NOT data and 0.17" in that from the WHT. The theoretical limit of NOT is 0.075" and that of WHT is 0.045". The NOT data was said to approach the diffraction limit, being 1.4 times larger, whereas the WHT failed to achieve near diffraction limited resolution. This was due to very weak signal and a lack of good seeing speckle images. Plate scales of 0.031" per pixel and 0.019" per pixel were achieved for images from NOT and WHT respectively.

A study of stellar variation through time, the analysis of the flux of a Blue Straggler Star through chronological cubes of data, was attempted. In this case the method failed to provide any clear results for the target star. An analysis time of less than 20 minutes was the maximum possible with our data and no recognisable change was observed during this time. Blue Straggler magnitude typically has periods of stability followed by turbulence with the shortest oscillation times approaching hours, hence a longer analysis time is recommended. The Blue Straggler studied had I Mag 16.77, making it among the dimmest in the catalogue, and large errors may have prohibited detection of the real change in flux through time. It is suggested that the method may be of use for the study of brighter variable stars over longer periods. A more successful study of variability with time has been made in a recent paper from the FastCam team at the IAC focussed on M15 by Diaz-Sanchez et al. 200 cubes of data were collected, allowing an evaluation over 100 minutes to be made with some periodic variation observed.

Spatial changes between Guhathakurta's Catalogue, 1992, and our FastCam Catalogue, 2008, were calculated and examined. There is no obvious movement towards the centre of the cluster, in fact the opposite is observed. It must be remembered that our data is a 2D representation of a 3D system and as such a definite conclusion cannot be drawn without a full 3D study. The average movement, movement being defined as the linear 2D change in star position between the two catalogues, per year is 1.99 milliarcseconds, 97.28km/s, and a negative correlation of motion with distance from the cluster centre is observed. Velocity dispersion also appears to be inversely proportional to distance, in agreement with observations in similar studies of Globular Cluster proper motion. Within the scope of this study it was not possible to make conclusions on the likelihood of a black hole central body.

These data sets were some of the earliest taken with FastCam and indicate the quality of results with a limited number of cubes. They are taken from among the first observational runs in the NOT and the very first in the WHT. More recent studies carried out by the FastCam team at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, such as the imaging of M15 by Diaz-Sanchez et al. 2011, have pushed this method further. In that particular investigation 200 cubes of data were used, producing a catalogue complete for magnitudes brighter than 19.3. The LuckyCam team from Cambridge University has pushed the limits of angular resolution in the 5.1m Palomar Telescope reaching a resolution of 0.035". Clearly the data examined in this report falls short of these results though plainly indicates the potential of the method some two years earlier and with approximately one tenth of the data. In particular, the high precision coordinates reported here lend themselves to a study of the internal dynamics of Globular Cluster M3 on a milliarcsecond scale. An insight into the prospective use of individual FastCam data cubes for the evaluation of flux variation is a further result of this report. With integration times as low as 15 seconds, a complete catalogue to over 16 mag is achievable in this dense stellar field with an error of 0.117 mag, an impossible aim with traditional imaging methods.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Appendix A: Final FastCam Catalogue

ID	RA	Dec	I Mag	Note	ID	RA	Dec	I Mag	Note
1	13:42:08.721	+28:22:44.11	11.4394		51	13:42:10.338	+28:22:54.18	16.6154	
2	13:42:08.980	+28:22:53.04	12.4532		52	13:42:10.340	+28:22:51.39	15.4564	
3	13:42:09.067	+28:22:44.83	15.8942		53	13:42:10.382	+28:22:44.18	13.3648	
4	13:42:09.075	+28:22:50.67	14.2204		54	13:42:10.408	+28:22:48.83	15.5351	RR
5	13:42:09.225	+28:22:48.72	16.4043		55	13:42:10.408	+28:22:51.28	16.521	
6	13:42:09.311	+28:22:44.89	16.0461		56	13:42:10.419	+28:22:46.41	14.4797	
7	13:42:09.322	+28:22:53.22	16.208		57	13:42:10.438	+28:22:42.99	15.1312	
8	13:42:09.352	+28:22:51.05	16.8099		58	13:42:10.444	+28:22:52.58	14.5327	
9	13:42:09.378	+28:22:44.38	14.0185		59	13:42:10.446	+28:22:59.77	16.0463	
10	13:42:09.427	+28:22:51.33	14.8925		60	13:42:10.457	+28:22:59.50	16.6388	RR
11	13:42:09.451	+28:22:49.69	15.9711		61	13:42:10.462	+28:22:50.04	13.9976	
12	13:42:09.477	+28:22:52.89	15.5881		62	13:42:10.476	+28:22:49.19	10.7693	
13	13:42:09.513	+28:22:44.45	15.058		63	13:42:10.513	+28:22:49.79	15.7719	
14	13:42:09.584	+28:22:50.02	16.1006		64	13:42:10.553	+28:22:58.70	16.6889	
15	13:42:09.597	+28:22:48.05	13.3128		65	13:42:10.588	+28:22:53.54	14.09	RR
16	13:42:09.623	+28:22:45.12	17.2643		66	13:42:10.641	+28:22:52.68	16.086	RR
17	13:42:09.676	+28:22:46.59	15.8179		67	13:42:10.656	+28:22:59.95	15.5946	
18	13:42:09.687	+28:22:44.16	16.8398		68	13:42:10.676	+28:22:51.25	16.0695	
19	13:42:09.692	+28:22:51.87	15.9417		69	13:42:10.741	+28:22:51.61	13.4212	
20	13:42:09.701	+28:22:47.40	15.08415		70	13:42:10.742	+28:22:51.58	16.2994	
21	13:42:09.728	+28:22:52.79	15.1903		71	13:42:10.747	+28:22:47.98	17.5591	
22	13:42:09.730	+28:22:45.34	16.6398		72	13:42:10.766	+28:23:00.28	16.4692	
23	13:42:09.745	+28:22:50.50	16.3879		73	13:42:10.777	+28:22:55.64	17.5031	
24	13:42:09.767	+28:22:45.57	17.1363		74	13:42:10.799	+28:22:58.89	16.2854	
25	13:42:09.811	+28:22:53.15	14.8496		75	13:42:10.814	+28:22:48.97	16.3596	
26	13:42:09.823	+28:22:50.75	17.2773		76	13:42:10.831	+28:22:49.94	16.5155	
27	13:42:09.855	+28:22:51.10	16.0206		77	13:42:10.849	+28:22:31.21	14.629	
28	13:42:09.858	+28:22:51.13	16.5463		78	13:42:10.851	+28:22:46.21	16.5308	
29	13:42:09.904	+28:22:48.12	15.15745		79	13:42:10.860	+28:22:39.52	16.0591	
30	13:42:09.915	+28:22:45.68	17.6048		80	13:42:10.875	+28:22:30.01	15.2234	RR
31	13:42:09.958	+28:22:46.85	14.6899		81	13:42:10.876	+28:22:44.20	15.7518	
32	13:42:10.035	+28:22:49.78	16.833		82	13:42:10.877	+28:22:29.72	16.7612	
33	13:42:10.052	+28:22:44.12	17.6602		83	13:42:10.888	+28:22:33.17	17.0255	
34	13:42:10.128	+28:22:52.39	14.2642		84	13:42:10.890	+28:23:00.51	15.8614	
35	13:42:10.135	+28:22:50.92	17.478		85	13:42:10.893	+28:22:31.98	17.0171	
36	13:42:10.137	+28:22:43.08	16.7717		86	13:42:10.893	+28:22:37.94	15.9911	RR
37	13:42:10.140	+28:22:46.79	13.2276		87	13:42:10.923	+28:22:41.38	13.5881	
38	13:42:10.160	+28:22:44.58	14.4069		88	13:42:10.934	+28:22:30.68	16.7484	RR
39	13:42:10.162	+28:22:41.03	17.4215	RR	89	13:42:10.939	+28:22:47.11	16.6579	
40	13:42:10.177	+28:22:48.42	17.5669		90	13:42:10.945	+28:22:40.63	15.8153	
41	13:42:10.179	+28:22:56.01	16.1464		91	13:42:10.947	+28:22:36.26	16.7037	
42	13:42:10.182	+28:22:53.64	17.1525		92	13:42:10.948	+28:22:34.88	17.5075	
43	13:42:10.191	+28:22:51.20	15.8127		93	13:42:10.955	+28:22:38.39	16.6889	
44	13:42:10.233	+28:22:52.37	16.0632		94	13:42:10.955	+28:22:52.94	14.1565	
45	13:42:10.233	+28:22:59.06	11.4633		95	13:42:10.971	+28:22:33.17	16.5984	BS
46	13:42:10.303	+28:22:56.73	16.9123		96	13:42:10.972	+28:22:43.28	15.845	
47	13:42:10.311	+28:22:59.09	14.1455		97	13:42:10.975	+28:22:51.42	16.4038	
48	13:42:10.318	+28:22:44.99	15.5023		98	13:42:10.979	+28:22:47.18	17.3035	
49	13:42:10.328	+28:22:51.21	12.1621		99	13:42:10.979	+28:22:58.10	15.6425	
50	13:42:10.330	+28:22:42.59	14.9962		100	13:42:10.984	+28:22:30.86	16.8086	

ID	RA	Dec	I Mag	Note	ID	RA	Dec	I Mag	Note
101	13:42:10.993	+28:22:57.07	14.8233		151	13:42:11.329	+28:22:33.60	12.7758	
102	13:42:11.000	+28:22:36.94	16.6809		152	13:42:11.341	+28:22:35.05	15.2982	
103	13:42:11.024	+28:22:53.44	15.5855		153	13:42:11.353	+28:22:40.86	14.7075	
104	13:42:11.029	+28:22:34.43	16.6074	RR	154	13:42:11.367	+28:22:33.49	16.0551	
105	13:42:11.062	+28:22:31.45	16.2682		155	13:42:11.376	+28:22:50.53	15.2258	
106	13:42:11.062	+28:22:45.44	15.2838		156	13:42:11.387	+28:22:37.78	14.4986	
107	13:42:11.065	+28:23:00.06	17.6517		157	13:42:11.390	+28:22:31.08	16.2024	
108	13:42:11.066	+28:22:42.14	15.8475		158	13:42:11.404	+28:22:47.39	15.1675	RR
109	13:42:11.066	+28:22:57.91	16.4296		159	13:42:11.405	+28:22:47.23	16.3825	
110	13:42:11.074	+28:22:37.76	14.5656		160	13:42:11.408	+28:22:33.20	15.4175	
111	13:42:11.075	+28:22:41.10	14.992		161	13:42:11.417	+28:22:30.22	16.3743	
112	13:42:11.077	+28:22:54.06	16.995		162	13:42:11.422	+28:22:54.28	16.0192	
113	13:42:11.078	+28:22:58.33	14.0541		163	13:42:11.424	+28:22:41.14	16.2411	
114	13:42:11.084	+28:22:44.41	15.5096	RR	164	13:42:11.424	+28:22:42.30	16.0528	
115	13:42:11.085	+28:22:37.01	16.0665		165	13:42:11.435	+28:22:58.78	16.3035	
116	13:42:11.086	+28:22:34.42	14.005		166	13:42:11.436	+28:22:32.56	16.6675	
117	13:42:11.098	+28:22:59.74	15.2754		167	13:42:11.441	+28:22:37.34	15.0457	
118	13:42:11.108	+28:22:50.05	16.0065		168	13:42:11.447	+28:22:38.59	16.3806	
119	13:42:11.119	+28:22:33.25	14.8477		169	13:42:11.449	+28:22:51.65	13.6439	
120	13:42:11.130	+28:22:34.41	17.4046		170	13:42:11.452	+28:22:38.80	16.6897	
121	13:42:11.133	+28:22:51.68	16.8216		171	13:42:11.454	+28:22:37.42	16.3657	
122	13:42:11.141	+28:22:34.09	13.0482		172	13:42:11.458	+28:22:47.46	15.1673	
123	13:42:11.147	+28:22:41.16	16.3834		173	13:42:11.472	+28:22:41.03	15.2299	
124	13:42:11.155	+28:22:58.40	15.0076		174	13:42:11.473	+28:22:47.63	16.3934	
125	13:42:11.167	+28:22:31.17	15.1026		175	13:42:11.484	+28:22:49.91	17.3839	
126	13:42:11.186	+28:22:37.47	16.7672		176	13:42:11.489	+28:22:34.47	14.5945	
127	13:42:11.188	+28:22:50.38	16.7334		177	13:42:11.491	+28:22:45.51	14.0199	
128	13:42:11.192	+28:22:35.30	16.7267		178	13:42:11.493	+28:22:40.23	16.7246	
129	13:42:11.195	+28:22:43.60	17.2215		179	13:42:11.499	+28:22:39.08	14.5366	
130	13:42:11.195	+28:22:47.23	12.2992		180	13:42:11.499	+28:22:49.89	15.1252	
131	13:42:11.195	+28:22:47.24	13.7368		181	13:42:11.503	+28:22:31.86	15.5772	
132	13:42:11.220	+28:22:45.75	15.8856		182	13:42:11.510	+28:22:38.49	15.4838	
133	13:42:11.224	+28:22:35.83	15.9144		183	13:42:11.511	+28:22:43.79	14.6476	
134	13:42:11.230	+28:22:48.05	15.4503		184	13:42:11.511	+28:22:51.88	15.0448	
135	13:42:11.230	+28:22:50.41	16.9305		185	13:42:11.512	+28:22:30.09	16.4346	BS
136	13:42:11.241	+28:22:37.12	16.6474		186	13:42:11.513	+28:22:40.10	17.0941	
137	13:42:11.242	+28:22:38.17	15.3109		187	13:42:11.514	+28:22:41.43	15.5483	
138	13:42:11.251	+28:22:29.51	16.7617		188	13:42:11.516	+28:22:44.14	16.4736	
139	13:42:11.251	+28:22:53.10	13.6998		189	13:42:11.528	+28:22:40.45	18.0117	
140	13:42:11.256	+28:22:57.40	14.672		190	13:42:11.531	+28:22:28.65	17.3381	
141	13:42:11.266	+28:22:31.21	16.7588		191	13:42:11.547	+28:22:36.31	15.585	
142	13:42:11.294	+28:22:43.68	15.7078		192	13:42:11.550	+28:22:40.33	15.7444	
143	13:42:11.299	+28:22:41.51	16.4943		193	13:42:11.555	+28:22:34.51	17.345	
144	13:42:11.303	+28:22:32.17	16.7705		194	13:42:11.557	+28:22:38.76	17.471	
145	13:42:11.307	+28:22:34.90	14.2492		195	13:42:11.565	+28:22:35.83	16.0168	
146	13:42:11.307	+28:22:51.01	16.4794		196	13:42:11.565	+28:22:41.17	16.1054	
147	13:42:11.313	+28:22:33.73	16.3749		197	13:42:11.568	+28:22:38.49	16.807	
148	13:42:11.314	+28:22:30.60	17.1119		198	13:42:11.589	+28:22:35.25	16.2814	
149	13:42:11.327	+28:22:29.70	17.6049		199	13:42:11.594	+28:22:30.31	17.395	
150	13:42:11.328	+28:22:46.21	16.393		200	13:42:11.594	+28:22:50.02	15.9228	

ID	RA	Dec	I Mag	Note	ID	RA	Dec	I Mag	Note
201	13:42:11.596	+28:22:43.79	15.895		251	13:42:11.819	+28:22:51.53	12.3103	
202	13:42:11.605	+28:22:44.03	13.8763		252	13:42:11.827	+28:22:46.22	16.8507	
203	13:42:11.606	+28:22:37.32	15.0811		253	13:42:11.830	+28:22:35.39	16.6349	
204	13:42:11.606	+28:22:42.41	15.9085		254	13:42:11.836	+28:22:56.00	16.5107	
205	13:42:11.609	+28:22:51.21	14.3071		255	13:42:11.837	+28:22:31.04	17.5218	
206	13:42:11.610	+28:22:48.26	17.7548		256	13:42:11.841	+28:22:46.35	17.9102	
207	13:42:11.614	+28:22:45.67	15.2327		257	13:42:11.841	+28:22:47.50	14.3931	
208	13:42:11.621	+28:22:35.37	16.2828		258	13:42:11.842	+28:22:39.56	16.0251	
209	13:42:11.626	+28:22:41.48	17.8314		259	13:42:11.846	+28:22:49.31	15.6865	
210	13:42:11.635	+28:22:34.96	17.5143		260	13:42:11.852	+28:22:48.17	16.2976	
211	13:42:11.644	+28:22:38.28	18.0029		261	13:42:11.855	+28:22:44.45	16.3912	
212	13:42:11.646	+28:22:52.20	16.5783		262	13:42:11.863	+28:22:34.32	16.3594	RR
213	13:42:11.667	+28:22:52.52	14.9931		263	13:42:11.868	+28:22:50.76	14.6185	
214	13:42:11.671	+28:22:41.04	16.8123		264	13:42:11.878	+28:22:48.86	13.3297	
215	13:42:11.682	+28:22:45.85	15.6486		265	13:42:11.883	+28:22:40.49	15.0849	
216	13:42:11.684	+28:22:51.22	17.1456		266	13:42:11.887	+28:22:32.07	16.0276	
217	13:42:11.685	+28:22:28.87	16.4974		267	13:42:11.913	+28:22:38.61	13.2467	
218	13:42:11.685	+28:22:35.10	15.6216		268	13:42:11.917	+28:22:30.96	15.0435	
219	13:42:11.692	+28:22:40.33	13.7121		269	13:42:11.920	+28:22:34.95	16.7387	
220	13:42:11.695	+28:22:37.54	15.2026		270	13:42:11.954	+28:22:40.92	14.5745	
221	13:42:11.698	+28:22:37.78	16.3061		271	13:42:11.956	+28:22:38.18	17.6207	
222	13:42:11.699	+28:22:44.75	15.2103		272	13:42:11.972	+28:22:37.27	17.5547	
223	13:42:11.700	+28:22:38.99	15.7727		273	13:42:11.973	+28:22:40.57	17.3967	
224	13:42:11.702	+28:22:50.46	16.8067		274	13:42:11.975	+28:22:51.33	15.5102	
225	13:42:11.704	+28:22:56.52	14.8072		275	13:42:11.989	+28:22:50.48	15.8503	
226	13:42:11.705	+28:22:39.67	16.482		276	13:42:11.993	+28:22:34.40	16.595	
227	13:42:11.733	+28:22:31.56	16.973	BS	277	13:42:11.998	+28:22:28.56	15.2026	
228	13:42:11.733	+28:22:36.67	15.1235		278	13:42:12.009	+28:22:37.52	16.5214	
229	13:42:11.734	+28:22:56.20	16.2058		279	13:42:12.014	+28:22:39.09	17.3046	
230	13:42:11.735	+28:22:48.14	15.7944		280	13:42:12.014	+28:22:46.31	13.4733	
231	13:42:11.738	+28:22:47.69	16.8327		281	13:42:12.023	+28:22:49.58	15.0298	
232	13:42:11.740	+28:22:37.03	15.1517		282	13:42:12.026	+28:22:50.47	11.886	
233	13:42:11.746	+28:22:38.56	12.0674		283	13:42:12.027	+28:22:31.99	15.3431	
234	13:42:11.747	+28:22:37.92	16.1017		284	13:42:12.046	+28:22:38.79	17.3183	
235	13:42:11.748	+28:22:32.52	17.718		285	13:42:12.050	+28:22:42.17	15.5136	
236	13:42:11.750	+28:22:39.72	16.3635		286	13:42:12.067	+28:22:46.95	15.08	
237	13:42:11.754	+28:22:31.76	17.3408		287	13:42:12.074	+28:22:48.89	13.1538	
238	13:42:11.763	+28:22:48.17	13.2773		288	13:42:12.077	+28:22:40.89	17.0108	
239	13:42:11.763	+28:22:53.54	14.5416		289	13:42:12.088	+28:22:50.01	16.0881	
240	13:42:11.767	+28:22:45.71	13.2094		290	13:42:12.094	+28:22:34.22	17.6007	
241	13:42:11.773	+28:22:39.64	16.7809		291	13:42:12.096	+28:22:47.62	17.0389	
242	13:42:11.775	+28:22:30.65	17.0539		292	13:42:12.096	+28:22:49.73	15.8498	
243	13:42:11.776	+28:22:46.30	11.3507		293	13:42:12.104	+28:22:30.27	16.5923	
244	13:42:11.779	+28:22:55.40	17.8286		294	13:42:12.108	+28:22:48.45	14.9805	
245	13:42:11.786	+28:22:52.08	17.6722		295	13:42:12.110	+28:22:41.33	17.206	
246	13:42:11.801	+28:22:32.67	15.9589		296	13:42:12.113	+28:22:35.55	16.9068	
247	13:42:11.801	+28:22:39.01	17.1073		297	13:42:12.162	+28:22:42.00	17.7835	
248	13:42:11.811	+28:22:54.99	14.9525		298	13:42:12.162	+28:22:42.77	16.5488	
249	13:42:11.817	+28:22:38.09	16.3828		299	13:42:12.165	+28:22:34.14	16.0611	
250	13:42:11.818	+28:22:50.71	15.2008		300	13:42:12.165	+28:22:45.99	15.5167	

ID	RA	Dec	I Mag	Note
301	13:42:12.167	+28:22:37.61	15.5015	
302	13:42:12.167	+28:22:50.89	14.9492	
303	13:42:12.173	+28:22:37.13	15.236	
304	13:42:12.181	+28:22:35.81	16.976	
305	13:42:12.194	+28:22:42.80	16.8749	
306	13:42:12.195	+28:22:35.51	16.479	
307	13:42:12.197	+28:22:47.13	15.4717	
308	13:42:12.206	+28:22:40.90	15.446	
309	13:42:12.210	+28:22:32.49	15.9766	
310	13:42:12.216	+28:22:33.06	14.9845	RR
311	13:42:12.218	+28:22:29.88	16.3048	
312	13:42:12.220	+28:22:45.07	15.6332	
313	13:42:12.223	+28:22:51.03	15.6665	
314	13:42:12.227	+28:22:34.48	16.0192	
315	13:42:12.227	+28:22:36.46	14.9575	
316	13:42:12.227	+28:22:38.17	15.1807	
317	13:42:12.229	+28:22:28.91	13.2467	
318	13:42:12.236	+28:22:44.14	16.3973	
319	13:42:12.250	+28:22:40.51	17.3061	
320	13:42:12.256	+28:22:41.75	14.949	
321	13:42:12.277	+28:22:29.10	17.69	
322	13:42:12.277	+28:22:31.11	17.1289	
323	13:42:12.279	+28:22:36.82	17.566	
324	13:42:12.311	+28:22:34.37	16.1925	
325	13:42:12.318	+28:22:46.41	14.9109	
326	13:42:12.327	+28:22:31.76	16.0646	
327	13:42:12.327	+28:22:35.01	16.5597	
328	13:42:12.340	+28:22:31.59	15.6886	
329	13:42:12.345	+28:22:37.46	14.5175	
330	13:42:12.362	+28:22:29.52	16.3685	
331	13:42:12.382	+28:22:33.43	14.5456	
332	13:42:12.403	+28:22:39.75	15.7687	

TABLE XVI: Full Catalogue for FastCam fields. BS: Blue Straggler from pre-existing catalogue. RR: RR Lyrae from pre-existing catalogue.